

Quality Assurance Mechanisms in Private Schools in Bangkok, Thailand

Fretche Perino Fanuga
Pangasinan State University - Open University Systems
fretche.fanuga@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the quality assurance mechanisms implemented by private schools in Bangkok, Thailand, focusing on their effectiveness in enhancing school management and educational standards. Specifically, it investigated the profile of private schools in terms of number of enrollees, teaching and non-teaching staff, teacher-student ratio, curriculum used, awards received, and extracurricular activities conducted. It also assessed the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms in four areas: learners' quality, instruction, educational administration and management, and learning and community development. Furthermore, the study explored the significant relationship between the implementation of quality assurance mechanisms and the

schools' profile variables and proposed a sustainability plan to improve quality assurance practices in private schools in Thailand. The study employed a mixed-methods research design utilizing both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Purposive sampling was used to select 201 teachers based on their knowledge, experiences, and perceptions regarding quality assurance practices in private schools. Data were gathered through a five-point Likert scale questionnaire and analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, mean scale, Chi-square statistics, and Spearman's rho correlation. Findings revealed that most schools had 301–500 students, 26 or more teaching staff, and 26 or more non-teaching staff, with a teacher-student ratio of 21–25. The Ministry of Education Curriculum Thailand (English Program) was the most commonly used curriculum. Most schools received 0–10 awards and conducted 21–30 extracurricular activities annually. Moreover, the four categories of quality assurance mechanisms were found to be highly implemented across the participating schools.

Keywords: *Quality Assurance, Quality Assurance Mechanisms, Private Schools in Bangkok, QAM, QA*

INTRODUCTION

Thailand, one of the most progressive nations in Southeast Asia, is not only known for its rich cultural heritage and unique natural beauty but also for its high-quality educational institutions. This makes it an ideal destination for students seeking brighter career opportunities at a reasonable cost. Thailand, with a population of 71.74 million (as of 2022), has Thai as its official language. Geographically located at the heart of continental Southeast Asia, Thailand spans about 1,600 km from its northernmost to its southernmost point and 870 km from east to west. Its coastline stretches over 1,875 km along the Gulf of Thailand and 740 km along the Andaman Sea, with more than 400 islands that have become popular tourist destinations. Thailand is often referred to as the "Land of Smiles," a nickname reflecting the nation's friendly and hospitable people. This endearing trait has earned the country recognition as the fifth "best

country for cultural heritage influence," which lauds its rich cultural legacy. A 2021 report from CEOWORLD Magazine (2021, January 31), based in New York, ranked Thailand as the fifth top country for cultural heritage influence out of 165 nations. Italy, Greece, Spain, and India were placed ahead of Thailand. The magazine praised Thailand for its abundant cultural history, emphasizing its beautiful beaches, unique cultural offerings, and lively nightlife. Key historical sites like Sukhothai, Ayutthaya, and Ban Chiang continue to draw visitors keen to explore the country's rich past.

In 2012, Thailand allocated 7.57% of its GDP to education, as reported by the UNESCO Institute of Statistics (UIS). The government invested 38.3% of this expenditure directly into student education. The country's education system requires nine years of schooling, starting at age six, and offers 12 years of free education, including primary and lower secondary levels.

Educational History and Reforms

Thailand stands out as one of the few nations that was never colonized by Western powers. As a result, the country's education system has developed with a strong emphasis on Thai culture and values. However, Thailand began modernizing its education system in the early 19th century by incorporating Western educational practices, particularly in higher education. The National Education Act of 1999 was a pivotal moment in shaping the current structure of Thai education. The curriculum consists of eight core subjects: Thai language, mathematics, science, social studies, religion and culture, health and physical education, arts, careers and technology, and foreign languages.

The National Education Act of 1999 emphasizes human development and the belief that every individual has the potential to learn and grow throughout their lives. The content of Category 4 in the second edition of the Education Management Guidelines (2009-2018), as outlined in Section 22, has been revised to place greater emphasis on enhancing the quality and standards of education, as well as expanding access to educational and learning opportunities. A key strategy for achieving these objectives is the implementation of education quality assurance, which plays a central role in improving the quality and standardization of Thailand's education system.

Education, as described by Princess Sirindhorn (2001), is a process through which individuals acquire knowledge and qualifications that contribute to their personal and social well-being. This notion underscores the importance of aligning educational objectives, including the qualifications of graduates, to address the knowledge, skills, and other qualities outlined by the curriculum. It is crucial to assure parents, stakeholders, and other relevant parties that graduates from a specific institution will be competent, ethical, and well-prepared to contribute positively to society and engage in social development in a rapidly globalizing world. Ensuring these qualities in graduates requires significant time, effective management, and long-term sustainability. Research into various aspects of education—such as subject matter, school environment, achievement metrics, and teaching practices—is essential, given the broad scope of the education field.

Thailand 4.0 and Its Educational Implications

In May 2016, the Thai government launched the Thailand 4.0 initiative, which seeks to overhaul the country's economy by emphasizing sustainable development and technological innovation. This policy forms part of a larger 20-year national strategy and the 12th National Economic and Social Development Plan (2017-2021). The plan focuses on reducing inequality, promoting eco-friendly growth, and striving for high-income status (The Economist, 2017). According to Jones and Pimdee (2016), Thailand's economic development can be broken down into three distinct phases. The first phase, Thailand 1.0, was largely agrarian, with the economy relying heavily on agriculture. The second phase, Thailand 2.0, saw a shift toward industrialization, focusing on manufacturing and other light industries. In the Third phase, Thailand 3.0, the country embraced globalization, emphasizing heavy industries and export-driven

growth. Building upon this, Thailand 4.0 seeks to foster innovation and sustainable development by prioritizing digital technologies, advanced industries, and eco-friendly growth, positioning Thailand as a competitive player in the global market. According to Puncibutr (2017), a shift in education is necessary to foster creative and analytical thinking. This approach aims to develop individuals who are capable of driving sustainable progress and making meaningful contributions to creating a more equitable and just society.

The Role of International Schools in Thailand

Thailand is home to approximately 170 international schools, including preschools, with an enrollment of around 66,700 students. While the majority of international schools are located in Bangkok, which boasts over 100 institutions, other popular tourist and expat destinations like Phuket, Krabi, and Chiang Mai also host a considerable number of international schools, making them accessible throughout the country (Cushman & Wakefield, 2024). International schools in Thailand cater to a wide range of curricula, offering British, American, International Baccalaureate (IB), and other systems such as Swiss, German, and French. This variety allows students from different backgrounds and educational preferences to receive tailored education (ISC Research, 2024). Many of these schools also provide boarding facilities. In addition to international schools, over 150 private schools are registered with Thailand's Office of the Private Education Commission, which oversees private education in the country.

Students in primary school are taught using a curriculum that is based on the "Basic Education Core Curriculum of 2008." During their primary school years, they will also take two national exams, and if they pass them, they will be awarded the Certificate of Primary Education. Lower and upper secondary students, on the other hand, must earn 41 credits in key areas, where one credit is equal to 40 hours of instruction per semester. At the conclusion of Grades 9 and 12, the National Institute of Educational Testing Service evaluates students using the Ordinary National Education Test (O-NET).

Expansion of International Schools

The international school market in Thailand has experienced significant growth, with projections indicating a market value of around 87 billion baht in 2024, a notable increase from the previous year. This growth is driven by rising demand for international curricula and the expansion of educational institutions into new regions (Khaosod English, 2024).

Student Enrollment in Public and Private Schools

In 2022, approximately 9.84 million students were enrolled in public schools across Thailand. Additionally, private education plays a key role in the system, with nearly 3,760 formal private schools and 7,868 non-formal private institutions present (Statista, 2022; Education Profiles, 2022).

Private School Enrollment Trends

Private schools are an important sector in Thailand's education system. In 2020, around 22.22% of primary school students attended private schools, emphasizing the significant role private education plays in the country (Trading Economics, 2020).

Market Research and Analysis

For a detailed understanding of the international schools market in Thailand, including aspects like fees, student demographics, and school growth, ISC Research provides comprehensive reports. These documents highlight both the challenges and opportunities within the sector (ISC Research, 2024).

Challenges in the Thai Education System

Inequality in educational opportunities remains a significant issue in Thailand. Economic disparities contribute to widening inequality across educational settings, particularly in rural areas. Fernquest (2017) argues that Thailand's education system is struggling to meet global standards, with students in smaller, rural schools often overlooked. This educational gap creates challenges in preparing students with lower proficiency levels to compete in the Thailand 4.0 economy. Research by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) shows that students in larger urban schools tend to outperform those in smaller, rural schools, a disparity often attributed to differences in resources and educational conditions. According to the 2012 results from the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), students in larger urban schools performed better than those in smaller rural schools. Specifically, large city schools saw a 21.3% improvement in performance since the previous assessment, while smaller city schools experienced a more modest increase of 16.1%. This performance gap could be attributed to the distinct classroom management strategies employed by each school. Rose (2014) argues that every school creates its own system for managing classrooms, which plays a key role in how effectively knowledge is delivered. Additionally, larger schools, with their higher student populations, typically have access to larger budgets, enabling them to invest more in resources. Larger schools tend to receive more funding compared to smaller ones, as their higher student enrollment numbers are directly linked to the education budget (S. Wittayasin, 2017). This additional funding allows bigger schools to invest more in resources and systems, improving the overall quality of education. In contrast, smaller schools, with fewer students, often have limited financial support, which may affect their ability to provide the same level of educational services.

Quality Assurance and Regulation in Education

The Office of National Education Standards and Quality Assessment (2017), which operates under the Office of the Prime Minister, plays a vital role in maintaining the quality of education in Thailand. ONESQA is responsible for establishing the standards and procedures for conducting external evaluations of educational institutions. Every educational institution is required to undergo external evaluations at least once every five years, with results made publicly available to promote transparency and accountability. Additionally, the Thai government is responsible for overseeing the regulation, administration, and management of private educational institutions, including those that offer general education. This includes assuring that these institutions meet specific quality standards. According to Section 43 of the National Education Act, the state is tasked with supervising, monitoring, and assessing the quality and standards of education. However, private institutions retain the autonomy to manage and operate their educational programs. These institutions are required to meet the same quality evaluation standards as public schools. The management and operation of institutions offering basic education are governed by the National Education Act, the Private School Act (No. 2), B.E. 2554, along with other relevant laws and regulations related to both formal and non-formal private education.

Thailand's education system has undergone significant evolution, particularly in response to the demands of modernization and globalization. While the country has made substantial progress, challenges such as inequality and access to quality education remain. The government's initiatives, such as Thailand 4.0, highlight the need for a more innovative and sustainable approach to education, guaranteeing that all students, regardless of background, have access to opportunities that prepare them for success in an increasingly competitive world. Assuring quality in education and addressing disparities in resources across different regions of the country will be key to achieving these goals.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to assess the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms in private schools in Bangkok, Thailand. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of private schools in Bangkok in terms of the following:
 - a. Number of enrollees;
 - b. Number of teaching staff;
 - c. Number of non-teaching staff;
 - d. Faculty-to-student ratio;
 - e. Type of curriculum used;
 - f. Number of awards received; and
 - g. Number of extracurricular activities conducted?
2. What is the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms in private schools in Bangkok in terms of:
 - a. Standards of learners' quality;
 - b. Standards of instruction;
 - c. Standards of educational administration and management; and
 - d. Standards of learning and community development?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms used by private schools and the school's profile variables?
4. What sustainability plan for the implementation of quality assurance mechanisms can be proposed to enhance or improve the management of private schools in Thailand?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis is tested at a 0.05 level of significance in its null form:

- There is no significant relationship between the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms used by private schools and the school's profile variables.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study is confined to the profile of private schools in Bangkok, including the following variables: number of enrollees, number of teaching staff, number of non-teaching staff, faculty-to-student ratio, type of curriculum used, number of awards received, and number of extracurricular activities conducted.

Additionally, the study focuses on the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms in private schools in Bangkok in terms of standards related to learners' quality, instruction, assessment, management, and learning development.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study are expected to provide valuable insights to the following stakeholders:

- **Ministry of Education in Thailand:** This study provides input for assessing and improving the quality assurance mechanisms in private schools in Bangkok, which could serve as a basis for future action research and policy-making.
- **Office of the Education Council (OEC):** The study may contribute to developing new policies for evaluating instructional methods, enhancing competitiveness, and creating educational laws.

- **Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC):** The results can assist in formulating proposals for policies and development plans aimed at enhancing the evaluation and monitoring of basic education.
- **Principals and School Heads:** School administrators could use the findings to refine the implementation of quality assurance mechanisms, improving the overall success of their institutions.
- **Teachers:** The study will provide teachers with insights into quality standards for student learning, helping them enhance teaching methods, instructional materials, classroom management, and the use of online platforms to meet students' learning needs.
- **Parents:** The study may offer valuable information that helps parents understand the quality assurance mechanisms in place at their children's schools, contributing to more informed decisions about education.
- **Researchers:** The findings will provide baseline data and quality standards for student learning, serving as a reference for future research on educational quality assurance.

Literature Review

Quality assurance (QA) in education plays a crucial role in ensuring that schools meet established standards and continuously improve their teaching and learning environments. In Thailand, particularly in private schools in Bangkok, QA mechanisms are influenced by both national and international frameworks. This chapter presents a review of related literature and studies, categorizing them into themes that highlight internal and external quality assurance, accreditation, and the challenges and opportunities in implementing QA mechanisms in private schools. It synthesizes key insights from relevant research, providing a solid foundation for understanding the educational quality landscape in Thailand, particularly in the context of private education.

The world is evolving, with advancements in technology shaping daily life and impacting educational systems globally. In this context, quality assurance in education becomes essential, particularly in Thailand, where the demand for continuous improvement is high, given the evolving economic and social dynamics. Education, being fundamental to all aspects of society, is a focal point of these changes. In Thailand, quality assurance (QA) in education aims to strengthen the skills, knowledge, and attitudes of learners, preparing them for the challenges of an increasingly globalized world. As Thailand faces both domestic and international changes, it is crucial for education systems, including private schools, to adopt quality assurance measures that ensure consistent standards. There is an urgent need to improve the quality of human beings at all levels, particularly education, which is the basis of the lives of children, adolescents, and adults. Whether in urban or rural settings, education must be adaptive to economic and social dynamics.

A key aspect of educational quality assurance in primary and secondary schools involves the organized execution of academic tasks, efficient administrative management, and continuous evaluation. This process guarantees that students develop the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies to meet the defined educational standards (Sewatanon et al., 2021).

Afriadi et al. (2023) suggest that systematic management of educational quality assurance helps institutions adjust their teaching strategies to meet educational standards and improve student learning results. This aligns with the principles outlined by the Office of the National Commission (2000), which emphasizes that effective education management fosters the development of critical thinking and problem-solving abilities, both of which are essential for success in the modern world.

The importance of accreditation in ensuring quality has been a prominent topic of discussion. In their study, Ngoc, Nguyen, and Hieu (2022) highlighted that accreditation plays a crucial role in enhancing school performance across Southeast Asia. They found that institutions with accreditation achieved higher student performance and demonstrated improved teacher effectiveness, emphasizing the significant role of accreditation bodies in maintaining quality standards.

Parental involvement has been identified as a crucial element in ensuring the quality of private schools. According to Pushpakumara, Gamage, and Jayasundara (2023), parents who are actively engaged in school governance contribute to the development of more effective learning environments. This view is echoed by Nir and Bogler (2012), who discovered that schools with high levels of parental involvement tend to achieve better educational outcomes and greater accountability.

Technology has become a crucial component in ensuring educational quality. According to Nguyen and Pham (2020), digital tools such as learning management systems and online platforms assist in simplifying administrative tasks, monitoring student progress, and enhancing communication among stakeholders. This conclusion supports findings from the European Commission (2020), which stated that digital integration enhances transparency and improves data-driven decision-making in schools.

On Thailand's Educational System

Thailand's education system is structured into three key levels: Prathom 1-6 (elementary school), Mathayom 1-3 (lower secondary), and Mathayom 4-6 (upper secondary). The Prathom 1-6 program spans six years, and public education was extended to nine years in 2003, with Mathayom 6 becoming a mandatory level for all students. The National Curriculum in Thailand covers a broad range of subjects, including Thai language, mathematics, science, and foreign languages, while placing emphasis on cognitive skills, self-learning strategies, and moral development. Recent reforms and the focus on educational quality assurance, as highlighted by the National Education Act (1999), aim to enhance the overall quality of Thai education and ensure that learners acquire the necessary skills and knowledge to thrive in a rapidly changing world.

The establishment of educational quality assurance mechanisms in Thai schools is a response to globalization and the need for continuous improvement. As Thai society faces rapid transformations, the role of quality assurance mechanisms becomes increasingly important in fostering critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and adaptability among students. Educational quality assurance ensures that Thai schools provide an environment conducive to learning and personal growth, aligning with national educational standards and international expectations.

With the development of information technology and the rate of change in the world today, globalization is taking place. Every nation must develop the ability to adapt to ever-changing Prepare yourself to tackle the challenges presented by the current global trend. The caliber of the personnel is the most important aspect of dealing with such changes and difficulties. Managing education to create excellent individuals is crucial to receiving a wonderful education. Thai learners will be better able to think critically, solve issues, and put their ideas into coherent sentences as a result, which will contribute to the development of each person's potential. These skills are essential for surviving in the modern world. Although there have been recent initiatives to raise the standard of Thai education, education in Thailand focuses on creativity, self-learning, the capacity to adapt to rapid change, ethics and morality, self-reliance, and the capacity to live happily. Because of this, it is essential to raise the standard of education in Thailand by implementing educational quality assurance, which will serve as a framework for monitoring and motivating educational institutions to maintain high standards of instruction at all times. In order to develop educational quality and standards at all levels, a national education law was established, which led to a significant reform of education that was centered on education quality (Office of the National Education Commission, 2000, page 1).

The administration and execution of initiatives in accordance with the standard mission of educational institutions to continuously raise the caliber of students is referred to as educational quality assurance. This is done to increase the trust of those who receive education services, stop the delivery of low-quality instruction, and make education a potent tool for the creation of a higher-quality population. To meet high-quality education standards, they must review and evaluate education implementation. The Importance and Definition of Educational Quality Assurance Article 81 of the Constitution of the Kingdom

of Thailand (BE 2540) stipulates that the government must provide education, training, and support for the establishment of "knowledge and morality," as well as provide national education laws, which led to the National Education Act of 1999. The establishment of a system of educational quality assurance to improve educational quality and standards at all levels results in a majority educational revolution that focuses on the quality of education. Section 47 of the National Education Act of 1999 defines educational quality assurance as the management and activities that are in line with the school's normal mission to keep improving the quality of its students. It also includes building trust in educational service recipients, both direct service recipients like students and parents and indirect service recipients like corporations, the population, and society as a whole. According to the National Education Act of 1999, educational institutions and affiliations must set up internal quality assurance systems and consider them an integral part of the continuing administration of education. At least once every five years, all educational institutions are subject to an external quality assessment. The National Education Act (1999, page 23) designates the Office for National Education Standards and Quality Assessment as the operator in this regard.

Studies by Cheng and Tam (1997) emphasize that education quality must be viewed holistically, involving administrative structures, teacher training, curriculum design, and student engagement. Tan and Dimmock (2000) also highlight that comparative education models reveal the importance of adopting flexible quality assurance mechanisms to address diverse learning environments.

Provision of Education by Private Educational Institutions

Private educational institutions in Thailand, including those offering both general education and vocational training, are held to the same standards of quality assurance as public schools. The government's responsibility is to oversee the management and quality of education in private schools, ensuring they meet the required standards. The National Education Act (1999) outlines the regulations for the establishment and operation of private schools, including the creation of internal quality assurance systems and the requirement for periodic external assessments.

The role of private educational institutions is becoming increasingly significant, particularly in urban areas like Bangkok. These institutions must not only maintain high academic standards but also align with national policies and accreditation systems to guarantee the quality of education they offer. Through accreditation and internal quality assurance practices, private schools can demonstrate their commitment to educational excellence.

The state is responsible for supervising management and administration as well as maintaining the standards and quality of private educational institutions, including those that offer both general education and vocational training. As stated in Section 43 of the National Education Act, "the administration and management of education by the private sector must have freedom, with the state being responsible for overseeing, monitoring, and evaluating educational quality and standards. Private educational institutions must adhere to the same standards and guidelines for evaluating educational quality. The National Education Act, the Private School Act (No. 2), B.E. 2554, and other laws and regulations pertaining to private education of both formal and non-formal types are currently used to establish and manage private educational institutions that offer basic education.

According to the Private School Act, a formal school must have an executive board made up of the licensee, manager, director, representatives of the teachers and parents of the students, as well as other qualified individuals. This is true of educational administration and management in private basic education institutions. The executive board is responsible for a number of tasks and responsibilities, such as issuing school rules and regulations, approving the school's policies and development plans for education, providing advice on school administration and management with regard to staffing, work schedules, finances, methods, student activities, buildings and premises, community relations, and more. The executive board also oversees the 35 formal schools that make up education in Thailand. A report from the

Office of the Private Education Commission showed that in the academic year 2015, there were 12,892 private institutions offering formal, non-formal, special, and welfare education.

The outcomes of the implementation of national education standards, the creation of educational standards for educational institutions, and requirements relating to educational quality for every educational institution that offers basic Education serves as a target or framework for setting standards for the school itself. To meet standards, the institution may add the particular qualities of the school in various fields.

Research by Bray (2002) indicates that private education often bridges gaps left by public institutions, providing alternative pathways to quality education. Similarly, James (2011) notes that the increasing privatization of education worldwide necessitates stringent quality assurance policies to prevent disparities in educational outcomes.

On the Quality Assurance Mechanisms Used in Private Schools

The Office for National Education Standards and Quality Assessment (ONESQA) plays a pivotal role in the external assessment of educational institutions in Thailand. Through internal and external quality assurance systems, ONESQA assures that private schools meet established criteria and that their educational practices align with national standards. Both internal quality assurance (IQA) and external quality assurance (EQA) mechanisms are crucial in maintaining educational quality and fostering institutional improvement.

IQA refers to the processes and strategies implemented within schools to monitor and improve quality, including curriculum development, teacher training, and performance assessments. External quality assurance, on the other hand, involves third-party assessments and accreditations that provide an objective evaluation of a school's adherence to national and international standards.

The Office for National Education Standards and Quality Assessment (Public Organization), also known as ONESQA, must be established in accordance with Section 49 of Chapter 6 on the Education Standards and Quality Assurance of the National Education Act, B.E. 2542 (A.D. 1999). Two changes were made to the National Education Act afterward: the Amendment (No. 2) of B.E. 2545 (A.D. 2002) and the Amendment (No. 3) of B.E. 2553 (A.D. 2010). These changes require ONESQA to come up with the criteria and method for external quality assessment (EQA) and to check the quality of educational institutions by evaluating the results of educational management while keeping in mind the goals, principles, and rules for education management. The internal quality assurance (IQA) criteria for education institutions are being successfully implemented, and EQA is a key tool to validate this. Additionally, it offers objectives for the improvement of learner identity and quality that are consistent with the purposes of the establishment of educational institutions. All parties involved and recipients of educational services will feel more secure about the caliber of the education being offered thanks to EQA. Moreover, fundamental ideas for the establishment of EQA standards and criteria have been incorporated into the policy framework for the reform of the quality assessment and quality assurance systems at all levels of educational institutions. EQA implementation is associated with the IQA system that educational institutions use, with the intention of reducing paper loads and duplication between the two systems. The new EQA system is made to represent the quality of the institutions as well as their IQA results and management outcomes in the context of the examined educational institutions. The public should have access to accurate and transparent data and information about the accomplishments of the evaluated educational institution. As a result, EQA will contribute to the improvement of the standards and overall quality of the evaluated educational institutions.

On Quality Assurance Mechanism Used in Schools

Quality assurance is about having systems to ensure that the assessment process is valid, reliable, and undertaken with integrity. Quality assurance establishes and maintains set requirements for developing

reliable products. A quality assurance system is meant to increase customer confidence and company credibility while also improving work processes and efficiency, and it enables a company to compete better with others (Gillis, 2019). Maintaining and enhancing their quality, equity, and efficiency entails conducting a comprehensive evaluation of educational programs and procedures. It involves thoroughly analyzing academic policies and procedures to preserve and boost their effectiveness, equity, and quality. Furthermore, it encompasses school self-evaluation, external evaluation, including inspection, the evaluation of teachers and school leaders, and student assessments (Quality Assurance, n.d.). To promote high-quality education, effective quality assurance mechanisms must be developed. Quality assurance is essential for accountability and supporting the ongoing development of schools, teaching, and learning. Well-functioning systems have tools to help balance vertical and horizontal, internal and external responsibility, and focus on development to support schools in adapting to the changing needs of learners over time (European Commission, 2020).

Internal Quality Assurance in Private Schools

Sirirattanchit (2024) examined the role of Internal Quality Assurance (IQA) in Thai basic education, emphasizing its importance in preparing institutions for external evaluation. The study highlights key IQA strategies such as teacher training, curriculum development, and performance assessments. It also underscores the necessity of a systematic approach to improve school credibility and meet national standards. Learttavisin, Niyamapha, & Buasuan (2019) analyzed how private schools in Bangkok implement IQA to comply with the School Evaluation and Quality Assurance System Reform. Their findings suggest that effective IQA practices involve regular self-assessment, faculty development, and the alignment of institutional goals with national policies.

External Quality Assurance and Accreditation

The role of external accreditation in ensuring educational quality is extensively discussed in Tanawong & Suthachai (2022), which compares private schools that have undergone accreditation with those that have not. The study found that accredited institutions tend to exhibit higher student performance, greater teacher retention, and stronger parent satisfaction. However, it also identified accreditation as a resource-intensive process, requiring significant investment in compliance and continuous improvement.

QAHE Insights (n.d.) provides an overview of international accreditation bodies that oversee educational quality in Thailand. The study highlights how private and international schools in Bangkok pursue QAHE accreditation to differentiate themselves from competitors. Accreditation enhances faculty qualifications and curriculum standards, making institutions more attractive to expatriate families seeking globally recognized education.

Challenges and Opportunities in Quality Assurance Implementation

Despite the advantages of quality assurance, challenges remain in the implementation of these mechanisms. Hemthong, Thanasatchawat, & Savatsomboon (2023) critically examined QA policies in Thai higher education and noted that excessive administrative requirements often hinder rather than enhance educational quality. Similar concerns are observed in K-12 education. "The Quality Assurance on the Standard of Private Schools in Bangkok" (2016) discusses the operational challenges faced by private schools in meeting both national and international accreditation standards. These challenges include high costs, resistance to change among faculty, and the complexity of aligning multiple QA frameworks.

Emerging Trends in Educational Quality Assurance

"Model for the Development of Educational Quality and Standards in Secondary Schools under the New Quality Assurance Framework" (2019) proposes an updated QA model that integrates data-driven

decision-making and stakeholder participation. The study argues that modern QA mechanisms should go beyond compliance by incorporating continuous feedback from students, parents, and educators. "Design of an Educational Quality Assurance System for Driving Policy of Educational Reform in Thailand: Theory-based Evaluation" (2023) highlights how policy-driven QA initiatives impact institutional development. The study suggests that Thailand's QA policies must be more adaptive to address the diverse needs of private and international schools.

Gaps in the Literature

Despite extensive research on quality assurance, several gaps remain:

1. Lack of comparative analysis
 - Many studies fail to compare private and public schools, especially regarding the effectiveness of quality assurance (QA) practices.
2. Limited focus on K-12 Private Schools
 - Some studies focus only on higher education or certain types of schools, not addressing the unique challenges faced by K-12 private schools.
3. Insufficient exploration of international accreditation
 - Several studies do not discuss how international accreditation bodies influence practices or how schools integrate national and international QA frameworks.
4. Lack of Empirical Data on Long-term impact
 - Many studies lack data on the long-term effects of QA practices on student outcomes, institutional reputation, and overall school performance.
5. Limited stakeholder perspectives
 - Some studies focus primarily on administrators, leaving out the perspectives of teachers, students, and parents in evaluating QA processes and their effectiveness.
6. Inadequate exploration of challenges in QA implementation
 - Several studies don't address the specific challenges schools face in maintaining or aligning with multiple accreditation systems, such as administrative burdens, resource limitations, or resistance to change.
7. Need for longitudinal and case study data
 - Many studies lack longitudinal research or detailed case studies, which are crucial for assessing the sustained impact of QA practices and accreditation on school performance.
8. Over-reliance on self-reported data
 - Some studies rely heavily on self-reported data from school personnel, which may introduce bias and limit the objectivity of findings.
9. Absence of cost-benefit analysis
 - There is little discussion of the financial implications of QA processes and accreditation, especially regarding the costs versus the benefits of pursuing multiple accreditation systems.
10. Limited Generalizability
 - Some studies focus on specific regions or school types (e.g., private schools in Bangkok), which limits the applicability of findings to other areas or school sectors.

These gaps suggest a need for more comprehensive, longitudinal, and multi-stakeholder research on quality assurance in Thai education, particularly in private schools.

Quality assurance in education consists of both internal and external evaluation mechanisms. Williams (2011) emphasized that external quality assurance ensures institutions meet national and international benchmarks, while internal quality assurance mechanisms help institutions self-regulate and continuously improve.

According to Rodhi et al. (2021), monitoring and evaluation are essential for quality assurance, providing measurable indicators to determine effectiveness and efficiency in school administration. This concept aligns with Widiatmaja (2019), who argued that regular assessment practices ensure that schools uphold high educational standards.

The role of teacher training in quality assurance cannot be overlooked. Ngoc et al. (2022) found that continuous professional development of educators leads to more effective teaching methodologies, thereby improving student learning outcomes. Similarly, Leyendecker, Ottevanger, and van den Akker (2008) suggested that fostering creativity and critical thinking in national curricula enhances education quality.

Governments play a significant role in ensuring educational quality assurance. The Asian Development Bank (2012) reported that regulatory frameworks in Southeast Asia provide a foundation for monitoring educational institutions and ensuring compliance with national standards. Furthermore, SEAMEO RIHED (2012) examined various quality assurance models in Southeast Asian countries, highlighting the importance of government policies in maintaining educational integrity.

Student learning outcomes are a key measure of quality assurance. Pushpakumara et al. (2023) emphasized that standardized assessments and competency-based evaluations provide valuable insights into institutional effectiveness. This aligns with Nguyen and Pham (2020), who argued that transparent data on student performance allows schools to make informed improvements.

Challenges in implementing quality assurance mechanisms exist. Nguyen and Pham (2020) noted that resource limitations, administrative constraints, and resistance to change hinder effective quality assurance. These findings are consistent with OECD (n.d.), which identified collaboration among schools as a potential solution for overcoming challenges and sharing best practices.

Quality assurance (QA) systems play a crucial role in enhancing the educational standards of schools, particularly in the context of private education in Bangkok. Sirirattanchit (2024) explores the role of Internal Quality Assurance (IQA) in Thai basic education, emphasizing the importance of IQA mechanisms in preparing schools for External Quality Assurance (EQA). The study highlights the significance of systematic IQA approaches, including teacher training, curriculum improvement, and performance assessments, which collectively enhance the credibility of schools and ensure they meet national educational standards. Sirirattanchit's findings are particularly relevant to private schools in Bangkok, where compliance with national standards is essential for maintaining accreditation and attracting students. However, the study does not provide a comparative analysis of IQA effectiveness between public and private schools or consider the impact of international accreditation bodies on IQA practices in Thailand.

Similarly, Hemthong et al. (2023) critically examine the role of QA in Thai higher education, questioning whether these mechanisms contribute to genuine educational improvement or merely create bureaucratic hurdles. The study finds that QA often leads to excessive administrative workloads, diverting resources from teaching and learning. Furthermore, QA policies are perceived more as compliance-driven processes rather than tools for enhancing educational quality. This research is insightful for private schools in Bangkok, as it emphasizes the balance between regulatory compliance and quality enhancement, a challenge many schools face when aligning with the requirements of the Office for National Education Standards and Quality Assessment (ONESQA). However, Hemthong et al. primarily focus on higher education, limiting the applicability of their findings to K-12 education.

In addition, the study "Ensuring Quality Education: Overview of Quality Assurance Agencies in Thailand" (n.d.) offers a comprehensive overview of the various quality assurance agencies in Thailand, such as ONESQA and international accreditation bodies. The research emphasizes how schools that meet both national and international accreditation standards tend to enjoy higher reputations and greater student enrollment. This is highly relevant to private schools in Bangkok, many of which seek international accreditation to enhance their competitiveness. However, the article does not explore how schools can

effectively navigate multiple accreditation systems or the long-term impact of dual accreditation on educational outcomes.

Another relevant study by Tanawong and Suthachai (2022) examines the impact of accreditation on the performance of private schools in Thailand. Their research shows that accredited private schools typically report better student performance and faculty retention, as well as higher levels of parent satisfaction. These findings are significant for private schools in Bangkok, which often rely on accreditation to differentiate themselves in a competitive market. However, the study does not address the challenges schools face in sustaining accreditation standards over time or the cost-benefit analysis of investing in multiple accreditation systems.

Lerttavisin et al. (2019) focus specifically on the internal quality assurance frameworks for private schools in Bangkok. Their research identifies key areas for improvement, including management systems, quality monitoring, and the development of student-centered education structures. The study's proposed guidelines for enhancing educational quality assurance are valuable for private schools seeking to align with policy frameworks and improve educational outcomes. However, the study's focus on private schools in Bangkok limits its broader applicability, and there is a lack of empirical data on the long-term impact of the proposed guidelines.

Taken together, these studies contribute valuable insights into the quality assurance mechanisms in Thai education, particularly within private schools in Bangkok. They provide a nuanced understanding of how internal and external QA systems, including accreditation processes, can influence educational quality. However, several gaps remain, particularly in terms of the comparative effectiveness of different QA frameworks, the challenges of aligning national and international standards, and the long-term impact of these systems on student outcomes. These gaps present opportunities for further research to explore the complexities of QA in the educational landscape of Bangkok.

Synthesis of Reviewed Literature and Studies

The literature reviewed presents a comprehensive perspective on quality assurance (QA) systems in education, focusing particularly on both internal and external evaluation processes within educational institutions. Several studies emphasize the complementary roles of internal quality assurance (IQA) and external quality assurance (EQA) in maintaining high educational standards. Williams (2011) argues that EQA ensures that institutions align with national and international standards, while IQA encourages schools to self-regulate and continuously enhance their practices. This dual approach is supported by Rodhi et al. (2021) and Widiatmaja (2019), who stress the significance of consistent monitoring, evaluation, and performance assessments to ensure that institutions maintain educational excellence.

Teacher professional development and training emerge as pivotal elements in enhancing educational quality. Research by Ngoc et al. (2022) and Leyendecker et al. (2008) highlights that the ongoing development of teachers' skills directly influences the effectiveness of teaching methods, which in turn improves student outcomes. Therefore, teacher training is integral to both internal quality assurance frameworks and the overall sustainability of high-quality education.

The role of government regulations in shaping quality assurance practices is another central theme in the literature. The Asian Development Bank (2012) and SEAMEO RIHED (2012) emphasize that regulatory frameworks are essential for ensuring educational institutions adhere to national quality standards. Such frameworks provide institutions with a clear structure for achieving and maintaining high educational quality.

The assessment of student learning outcomes is identified as a fundamental measure of institutional effectiveness. Studies by Pushpakumara et al. (2023) and Nguyen and Pham (2020) argue that standardized assessments and transparent reporting of student performance are crucial for evaluating how well schools achieve their educational goals. These evaluations empower schools to make informed decisions about where improvements are needed.

Despite these advantages, the implementation of QA systems faces various challenges. Resource limitations, administrative burdens, and resistance to change are frequently cited as obstacles to effective QA. Nguyen and Pham (2020) and OECD (n.d.) suggest that collaboration between schools and the sharing of best practices can help mitigate these challenges and foster a more effective quality assurance environment.

In the specific context of private education in Bangkok, studies by Sirirattanchit (2024) and Hemthong et al. (2023) highlight the importance of both internal and external QA processes in ensuring that schools meet accreditation requirements. These processes are crucial for private schools to maintain their reputations and remain competitive, especially as international accreditation becomes increasingly important.

Accreditation, both domestic and international, has been shown to significantly impact private schools, as noted by Tanawong and Suthachai (2022). Their research found that accredited schools tend to have better student outcomes, higher faculty retention, and greater parental satisfaction. However, the process of maintaining accreditation is resource-intensive and it may sometimes lead to bureaucratic processes that detract from the primary focus of teaching and learning, as suggested by Hemthong et al. (2023).

In summary, the integration of IQA and EQA mechanisms is vital to ensuring that schools comply with standards and continuously improve their educational practices. Teacher development, government regulation, and the evaluation of student outcomes are key contributors to the effectiveness of these QA systems. However, challenges such as resource constraints, administrative burdens, and the potential for QA systems to become overly bureaucratic must be addressed to maximize the effectiveness of quality assurance in education.

To conclude, the literature reviewed offers valuable insights into the complex landscape of quality assurance in education, particularly within the context of private schools in Bangkok. The combined use of internal and external QA mechanisms is crucial for ensuring that institutions meet national standards while striving for ongoing improvement. Teacher professional development, governmental policies, and the regular assessment of student outcomes are all fundamental components of these QA systems.

Despite the benefits, several challenges remain in implementing these systems, including limited resources, administrative obstacles, and resistance to change. Furthermore, while accreditation plays a critical role in enhancing a school's reputation, there is a need for further research into the long-term effects of QA systems, particularly regarding student outcomes and the sustainability of accreditation standards.

The findings point to several areas for future exploration, including a deeper analysis of the comparative effectiveness of various QA systems, the challenges of managing multiple accreditation processes, and the long-term impact of QA frameworks on student achievement. Addressing these gaps will offer a more nuanced understanding of how quality assurance mechanisms can be refined and optimized in the Thai educational context, particularly in private schools in Bangkok.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the study is illustrated in a paradigm in Figure 1. The figure shows quality assurance mechanisms in private schools in Bangkok. The figure illustrates the extent to which quality assurance mechanisms are implemented in private schools in Bangkok, Thailand, with respect to the standards of learners' quality, instruction, administration and management, and learning and development. The profile of respondents should be determined by the hypotheses.

Figure 1. *Research Paradigm of the Study*

METHODS

Research Design

This study used a mixed-methods research strategy that will include qualitative and quantitative approaches, a descriptive survey used to gather data and information on the present existing condition of the quality assurance mechanism of private schools in terms of the schools' profile, the four standards; learners' quality, instructions, educational administration and management and learning and community development.

This study made an attempt to find the significant relationship between the level of implementation of the quality assurance mechanisms used by the private schools and the school profile variables.

The four quality assurance standards (Learners' Quality, Instruction, Educational Administration and Management, and Learning and Community Development) were the independent variables and the school profiles (Number of Enrollees, Number of Teaching Staff, Number of Non-Teaching Staff, Faculty-Student Ratio, Type of Curriculum used, Number of Awards received, and Number of Extracurricular activities conducted) were the dependent Variables.

Respondents of the Study

There were 201 teachers and school heads involved in this study from different private schools in Bangkok, Thailand as shown in Table 1.

Research Instruments

The questionnaire was utilized as the main instrument of the study. There was one set of questionnaires with two parts that was used in gathering the data. The first part was the profile of the respondents in private schools in Bangkok. The second part was the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms in private schools in Bangkok, Thailand.

Content validity was used to determine and ascertain the level to which the content or topic of the questionnaire was truly representative of the content of the main idea. It involved essentially, the systematic examination of the items to determine whether they covered a representative sample to be measured.

Five experts in the education industry validated the instruments. These experts were not part of the defense panel at the institution.

Data Gathering Procedures

After the permission was sought from the principals and heads of schools, the researcher prepared the instruments to be used. The questionnaire was prepared through a Google Form and sent to the respondents via email along with a letter asking permission from the respondents to be part of the study. Once answered, the data were retrieved and consolidated.

Interview was conducted for more verification of the information needed to validate the specified answer to the questionnaire.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In order to obtain the most significant results and findings, appropriate statistical tools were employed in the analysis of the data. This has ensured that the results have represented the true picture of the situation or condition under study.

To answer problem No. 1 on the profile of private schools in Bangkok, Thailand, it was measured using simple frequency counts and corresponding percentages.

For problem No. 2, on the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms in private schools in Bangkok, Thailand, frequency counts and percentages were computed for each scale. Further, the average weighted mean was computed and described using the table of mean scale values. The table is indicated below:

Mean Scale	Range	Description
5	4.51 – 5.00	Very Highly Implemented
4	3.51 – 4.50	Highly Implemented
3	2.51 – 3.50	Moderately Implemented
2	1.51 – 2.50	Slightly Implemented
1	1.00 – 1.50	Least Implemented

Utilizing Chi-square statistics and Spearman's rho correlation for problem No. 3 examined the significance of the relationship between the degree of quality assurance mechanisms implementation in private schools and their profile variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Private Schools in Bangkok, Thailand

This table presents the data on the profile of the private school in Bangkok, Thailand, in terms of the following variables: number of enrollees, number of teaching staff, number of non-teaching staff, teacher-student ratio, type of curriculum offered, number of awards received, and number of extra-curricular activities undertaken per year.

Number of Enrollees. As shown in Table 1, 1.5% of the number of enrollees are 0 to 100 students, 17.4% are 101 to 300 students, 27.4% are 301 to 500 students, 14.9% are 501 to 1000, 16.9% are 1001 to 2000, and 21.9% are 2001 students or more.

Number of Teaching Staff. According to Table 1, 4% of the number of teaching staff are 0 to 10, 16.4% are 11 to 15, 17.4% are 16 to 20, 16.9% are 21 to 25, and 45.3% are 26 and above.

Number of Non-Teaching Staff. Table 1 displays that 17.4% of the non-teaching staff are 0 to 10, 23.4% are 11 to 15, 13.4% are 16 to 20, 13.4% are 21 to 25, and 32.3% are 26 and above.

Table 1. *Profile of Bangkok Private Schools*
n= 201

Variables	Categories	Frequencies	Percentage
Number of Enrollees per Year	0-100	3	1.5
	101-300	35	17.4
	301-500	55	27.4
	501-1000	30	14.9
	1001-2000	34	16.9
	2001 and more	44	21.9
Number of Teaching Staff	0-10 teacher	8	4.0
	11-15 teachers	33	16.4
	16-20 teachers	35	17.4
	21-25 teachers	34	16.9
	26 and above	91	45.3
Number of Non-Teaching Staff	0-10	35	17.4
	11-15	47	23.4
	16-20	27	13.4
	21-25	27	13.4
	26 and above	65	32.3
Teacher-Student Ratio	1 teacher: 0–10 student	12	6.0
	1 teacher: 11–15 student	21	10.4
	1 teacher: 16–20 student	53	26.4
	1 teacher: 21–25 student	70	34.8
	1 teacher: 26–30 student	45	22.4
Type of Curriculum	American Curriculum	33	16.4
	Ministry of Education Curriculum Thailand (Bilingual and Mini-Bilingual Programme)	42	20.9
	Ministry of Education Curriculum Thailand (English Program)	46	22.9
	National Curriculum for England	36	17.9
	British Columbia Curriculum (BC Canada)	21	10.4
	International Baccalaureate Curriculum (IB)	7	3.5
	Singapore Curriculum	3	1.5
	Australian	3	1.5
	Canadian	2	1.0
	K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum	1	0.5
	Cambridge Curriculum	1	0.5
	Canadian Curriculum and Thailand English Program	1	0.5
	CBSE	1	0.5
	Child and Life-centered	1	0.5
	Ontario Curriculum	1	0.5
Singapore / UK	1	0.5	
Singapore/British Curriculum	1	0.5	
Number of Awards Received	0-10	64	31.8
	11-15	45	22.4
	16-20	38	18.9
	21-25	16	18.0
	26 -30 and above	38	18.9

Number of Extracurricular Activities	0-10	22	10.9
	11-20	72	35.8
	21-30	76	37.8
	31-40	17	8.5
	41 above	14	7.0

Teacher-Student Ratio. Table 1 demonstrates that the majority of respondents' schools have a faculty teacher-student ratio of 1 teacher to 21 to 25 students with 70 (34.8%), 1 teacher to 16 to 20 students with 53 (26.4%), 1 teacher to 26 to 30 students with 45 (22.4%), 1 teacher to 11 to 15 students with 21 (10.4%), and 1 teacher to 0 to 10 students with 12 (6%) as the faculty teacher-student ratio.

Type of Curriculum. As shown in Table 1, the majority of respondents' schools used the Ministry of Education Curriculum Thailand (English Program) with 46 (22.9%), 36 (17.9%) the National Curriculum for England, 21 (10.4%) the British-Columbia Curriculum (BC Canada), 7 (3.5%) the International Baccalaureate Curriculum (IB), 3 (1.5%) the Singapore Curriculum, 3 (1.5%) the Australian Curriculum, 2 (1.0%) the Canadian, and 1 (0.5%) shared with other curriculums by K–12 Basic Education Curriculum, Cambridge Curriculum, Canadian Curriculum, and Thailand English Program, CBSE, Child and Life-centered, Ontario Curriculum, Singapore/UK, and Singapore/British Curriculum.

Number of Awards Received. Table 1 displays the number of awards each responding school has received, as well as the total number of respondents. 64 (31.8%) of the participants received awards between 0 to 10, 45 (22.4%) between 11 to 15, 38 (18.9%) between 1 to -20, 16 (8.0%) between 21 to 25, and 38 (18.9%) between 26 and above.

Number of Extracurricular Activities Conducted. According to Table 1, respondents listed the number of extracurricular activities that their respective schools held each year. 22 (10.9%) in activities ranging from 0 to 10, 72 (35.8%) in activities ranging from 11 to 20, 76 (37.2%) of participants engaged in activities ranging from 21 to 30, 17 (8.5%) in activities ranging from 31 to 40, and 14 (7.0%) in activities ranging from 41 and above.

Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanism in Private Schools in Bangkok, Thailand

The quality assurance standards in private schools are divided into four categories: standards of learners' quality, standards of instruction, standards of educational administration and management, and standards of learning and community development. The data gathered along this line is presented in the succeeding tables.

Tables 2–9 highlight the indicators for Standards on Learners' Quality which focuses on Standard 1: Learners should have virtues, morality, and desirable values. Standard 2: Learners should be conscious of environmental preservation and development. Standard 3: Learners should have a working skill, love to work, be able to work with others, and have a good attitude toward an honest occupation. Standard 4: Learners should have the ability to think analytically and synthetically, have a good sense of judgment, be creative and thoughtful, and have a vision. Standard 5: Learners should have the necessary knowledge and skills as prescribed by curricula. Standard 6: Learners should have a skill for self-learning and love to learn and self-develop continuously. Standard 7: Learners should have healthy habits and good physical and mental health. Standard 8: Learners should have a sense of aesthetics and a disposition for art, music, and sport.

Table 2. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Learners' Quality in terms of Standard 1*

S1 — The learners should have virtues, morality, and desirable values.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school imposed discipline, responsibility, and observation of the basic precepts of their learners' religion.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	36 (17.9%)	46 (22.9%)	115 (57.2%)	4.35	Highly Implemented
2. The school values learners' honesty.	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	33 (16.4%)	37 (18.4%)	131 (65.2%)	4.49	Highly Implemented
3. The school values learners' sense of gratitude.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	32 (15.9%)	41 (20.4%)	124 (61.7%)	4.42	Highly Implemented
4. The school values their learners' acts of loving kindness, generosity, and willingness to sacrifice for the common good.	0 (0%)	3 (1.5%)	37 (18.4%)	37 (18.4%)	124 (61.7%)	4.4	Highly Implemented
5. The school encourages learners' thriftiness and keenness to engage in worthwhile uses of personal and private resources.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	42 (20.9%)	51 (25.4%)	104 (51.7%)	4.27	Highly Implemented
6. The school encourages their learners to take pride in Thai identity, appreciate Thai wisdom, and be loyal toward Thainess and the preservation of Thai identity.	0 (0%)	1 (0.5%)	43 (21.4%)	50 (24.9%)	107 (53.2%)	4.31	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.37	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Table 2 shows that Standard 1 of the Quality Assurance Standards for private schools says that students have good morals and values. The average weighted mean score for this standard is 4.37, which means that it is “Highly implemented.” This indicates that the school places a strong emphasis on strengthening the virtues, morality, and desirable behavior of its students. The study suggests that, to thrive in today’s society, it is crucial to improve the quality of human development at all levels, especially in education, which serves as the foundation for the lives of children, young people, and adults. Skills for leading a fulfilling life in society are essential, particularly as Thai society is poised to undergo significant changes that will impact the learning styles of future generations.

Whether in rural or urban communities, all Thai citizens—children and adults alike—must be able to continue learning and developing in response to Thailand's economic and social dynamics. Such development is especially important in a competitive, high-quality open economy, which will drive the learning needs and processes of nearly all Thai people. The future society will reflect these changes as well.

In indicator 2, the school values learners' honesty, which received a weighted mean of 4.49. Then in indicator 3, with assessing the school's emphasis on learners' sense of gratitude earned a weighted mean of 4.42, which was also rated as "highly implemented." Furthermore, the school encourages acts of loving kindness, generosity, and a willingness to sacrifice for the common good, which garnered a weighted mean of 4.40 in indicator 4. The school also places importance on discipline, responsibility, and adherence to the fundamental principles of students' religion, with a weighted mean of 4.35 as shown in indicator 1, indicating that these values are emphasized. This evidence suggests that private school teachers in Bangkok respect their students' religious beliefs.

The data also reveal that the primary goal of private schools in Bangkok is to support the welfare of their learners. In addition, with indicator 6, it can be concluded that respondents from private schools in Bangkok strongly encourage students to take pride in their Thai identity, appreciate Thai wisdom, and remain loyal to the preservation of Thai culture. This trend was reflected in a weighted mean of 4.31, which was also classified as "highly implemented." It appears that private school teachers in Bangkok actively promote the value of being a Thai citizen.

Lastly, in indicator 5, private school teachers in Bangkok encourage learners to practice thriftiness and make wise use of personal and private resources, as shown by a weighted mean of 4.27, which is still considered "highly implemented."

Table 3. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Learners' Quality in terms of Standard 2*

S2. Learners should be conscious of environmental preservation and development.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school conducts learning activities that show appreciation for the environment and awareness of the impacts of environmental changes.	0 (0%)	3 (1.5%)	37 (18.4%)	65 (32.3%)	96 (47.8%)	4.26	Highly Implemented
2. The school promotes learners' participation in activities and projects of environmental preservation and development.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	34 (16.9%)	72 (35.8%)	91 (45.3%)	4.24	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.25	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

As shown in Table 3, which reflects the level of implementation of quality assurance standards in private schools, Standard 2 (that learners should be conscious of environmental preservation and development) has an average weighted mean of 4.25. This figure indicates a strong focus on teaching students the importance of environmental preservation and development. The table shows that the indicator 1, which measures how well the school does with learning activities that help students care about the environment and understand how changes in the environment affect it, got a weighted mean of 4.26, which means it was “highly implemented.”

Indicator 2, which evaluates the school’s promotion of students’ involvement in environmental preservation and development activities, reveals that private schools in Bangkok actively involve their students in ecological awareness activities. This finding is reflected in the weighted mean of 4.25, demonstrating that these learning activities significantly impact both the students and the environment. The evidence suggests that the majority of private school teachers in Bangkok not only focus on the academic success of their students but also emphasize the importance of environmental consciousness.

Furthermore, private school teachers in Bangkok consider the implementation of indicator 2, which focuses on students’ involvement in environmental preservation efforts, highly effective. Promoting environmental awareness among students is crucial in nurturing environmentally responsible citizens.

As you can see from table 4, which is on the next page, the data collected for Standard 3, a lot of private school teachers in Bangkok think that teaching students how to do things with pride is an important area to focus on. This is shown by the fact that indicator 3 has a weighted mean of 4.42.

In indicators 1 and 4, private school teacher respondents indicated that learners develop skills for managing and completing work, as well as managing to work effectively. With weighted means of 4.3 and 4.32, respectively, these results suggest a high level of implementation. Developing management and completion skills is beneficial to students' academic and personal success.

Table 4. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Learners’ Quality in terms of Standard 3*

S3. Learners should have a working skill, love to work, be able to work with others, and have a good attitude toward honest occupations.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The learners develop skills for managing and completing work.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	37 (18.4%)	54 (26.9%)	106 (52.7%)	4.3	Highly Implemented
2. The learners develop perseverance, diligence, endurance, and mindfulness while working.	0 (0%)	6 (3.0%)	42 (20.9%)	61 (30.3%)	92 (45.8%)	4.19	Highly Implemented
3. The learners develop an attitude of working with happiness, developing their work, and being proud of their own work.	1 (0.5%)	2 (1.0%)	28 (13.9%)	51 (25.4%)	119 (59.2%)	4.42	Highly Implemented

4. The learners manage to work well with others.	1 (0.5%)	5 (2.5%)	29 (14.4%)	60 (29.9%)	106 (52.7%)	4.32	Highly Implemented
5. The learners are geared toward developing a good attitude toward honest occupations and searching for knowledge related to their interests.	0 (0%)	5 (2.5%)	32 (15.9%)	66 (32.8%)	98 (48.8%)	4.28	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.30	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Additionally, it was noted in indicator 5 that private school teacher respondents in Bangkok focus on developing perseverance, diligence, endurance, and mindfulness in learners while working—qualities that are highly valuable. The weighted mean of 4.28 shows that these qualities significantly contribute to students' overall academic and personal growth.

The overall weighted mean of 4.30 for Standard 3 demonstrates that these characteristics help students overcome challenges, stay focused, and maintain a positive mindset. Cultivating these qualities can, therefore, promote perseverance by encouraging a growth mindset, providing constructive feedback, and fostering resilience.

On the next page, Table 5 presents the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms among private school teachers in Bangkok. Regarding Standard 4, learners should possess the ability to think analytically and systematically, have good judgment, be creative and thoughtful, and have vision. The weighted mean of 4.18 for indicators 1 and 4 of this standard shows that most private school teachers in Bangkok strongly support activities that help students think more critically, methodically, conceptually, synthetically, and holistically. These activities should also help students be more creative, optimistic, and imaginative.

Table 5. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Learners' Quality in terms of Standard 4*

S4. Learners should have the abilities to think analytically and synthetically, have a good sense of judgment; be creative and thoughtful; and have a vision.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school promotes activities that develop learners' ability to think analytically, synthetically, conceptually, systematically, and holistically.	0 (0%)	8 (4.0%)	23 (11.4%)	95 (47.3%)	75 (37.3%)	4.18	Highly Implemented

2. The school develops the learners' ability to predict, set a goal, and use a method of decision-making.	0 (0%)	9 (4.5%)	35 (17.4%)	84 (41.8%)	73 (36.3%)	4.1	Highly Implemented
3. The school develops learners' ability to evaluate and make decisions and to solve problems calmly.	0 (0%)	10 (5.0%)	41 (20.4%)	56 (27.9%)	94 (46.8%)	4.16	Highly Implemented
4. The school develops learners' creativity, optimism, and imaginativeness.	1 (0.5%)	8 (4.0%)	38 (18.9%)	61 (30.3%)	93 (46.3%)	4.18	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.16	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

A weighted mean of 4.16 indicates that private school teachers in Bangkok believe they are effectively developing their students' capacity to assess and solve problems calmly.

In addition, the development of learners' ability to predict, set goals, and use decision-making methods reflects a weighted mean of 4.10. This implies that while private school teachers in Bangkok still implement this standard, they focus less on it compared to other aspects, though it remains highly implemented.

Looking at the overall weighted mean for Standard 4, private school teachers in Bangkok perceive that their learners possess the abilities to think analytically and synthetically, have good judgment, are creative and thoughtful, and have vision. With an overall weighted mean of 4.16, this standard is considered highly implemented.

As shown in Table 6 on the next page, it indicates that for Indicator 3, private school teachers in Bangkok ensure the development of learners' ability to communicate through listening, reading, speaking, writing, and other means. This indicator garnered a weighted mean of 4.28, suggesting that teachers believe the learners have acquired these four language skills.

Moreover, the respondents believe they have highly implemented the development of learners' optimum level of achievement and learning based on the established criteria. The result implies that the majority of private school teachers in Bangkok place significant emphasis on improving students' learning quality to help them achieve more academically.

In Indicator 4, private school teachers in Bangkok firmly believe that they are developing learners' ability to communicate in both Thai and other foreign languages, particularly English, which is considered a universal language. This indicator garnered a weighted mean of 4.16.

Table 6. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Learners' Quality in terms of Standard 5*

S5. Learners should have the necessary knowledge and skills as prescribed by curricula.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school develops learners' averages up to the optimum level of achievement and level of learning based on the set criteria.	0 (0%)	3 (1.5%)	39 (19.4%)	67 (33.3%)	92 (45.8%)	4.23	Highly Implemented
2. The school sets the average national Scholastic Aptitude Test (SAT) scores up to set criteria.	6 (3.0%)	22 (10.9%)	60 (29.9%)	57 (28.4%)	56 (27.9%)	3.67	Moderately Implemented
3. The school ensures the development of the learners' ability to communicate through speaking, writing, or other means.	1 (0.5%)	3 (1.5%)	32 (15.9%)	68 (33.8%)	97 (48.3%)	4.28	Highly Implemented
4. The school develops the learners' ability to communicate through both Thai and foreign languages.	1 (0.5%)	5 (2.5%)	39 (19.4%)	72 (35.8%)	84 (41.8%)	4.16	Highly Implemented
5. The school develops the learners' ability to use IT technology to develop learning.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	52 (25.9%)	80 (39.8%)	65 (32.3%)	4.02	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.07	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Additionally, Indicator 5 of the same table suggests that private school teachers in Bangkok are working to develop learners' ability to use information technology (IT) to facilitate learning, with a weighted mean of 4.02. However, it can be deduced from Indicator 2, where the schools set the average National Scholastic Aptitude Test (nSAT) based on specific criteria (reflected by a weighted mean of 3.67), that private schools in Bangkok may need to pay more attention to this standard indicator.

Finally, the overall weighted mean of 4.07 indicates that private school teachers in Bangkok have highly implemented all the set indicators for Standard 5.

Table 7. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Learners' Quality in terms of Standard 6*

S6. Learners should have a skill for self-learning and love to learn and self-develop continuously.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school develops in their learners the love of reading, writing, and listening; they know how to ask a question to learn the reasons.	1 (0.5%)	5 (2.5%)	37 (18.4%)	65 (32.3%)	93 (46.3%)	4.21	Highly Implemented
2. The school develops the learners' interest in seeking knowledge from different sources and their ability to use a library, other knowledge sources, and media both inside and outside school.	0 (0%)	11 (5.5%)	32 (15.9%)	62 (30.8%)	96 (47.8%)	4.21	Highly Implemented
3. The school develops in their learners the ability to have their own learning methods, be able to learn with others, and love to come to school.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	39 (19.4%)	54 (26.9%)	104 (51.7%)	4.28	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.23	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

As shown in Table 7, the data present the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanism standards in private school teachers in Bangkok, specifically on how the learners have skills for self-learning, love to learn, and continue self-development as stipulated in Standard 6. Looking at the information we collected, we found that a 4.21 weighted mean in indicator 1 means that private school teachers in Bangkok really worked to get their students to love reading, writing, listening, and asking questions to learn. This means the most of the teachers this is a big part of improving the quality of their students' education.

It is noticeable that indicator 2 has the same garnered weighted mean of 4.21, which also means that they assumed a very high implementation on the development of the learners' ability to seek knowledge from different sources such as libraries and media both inside and outside the school. This outcome suggests that a large number of private school respondents in Bangkok give undeniable regard to developing students' abilities to obtain knowledge in many different ways apart from what the teacher presents in the classroom, which can help them achieve more knowledge.

Lastly, in the same table, private school teachers in Bangkok perceived that they have very high implementation on the development of the students' ability to acquire their own learning methods, to learn with others, and to learn to love to come to school, obtaining a 4.28 weighted mean. This data implies that private school teachers in Bangkok predominantly consider that students should develop decision-making skills that will ultimately help them accomplish quality learning.

Table 8. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Learners' Quality in terms of Standard 7*

S7. Learners should have healthy habits and good physical and mental health.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school implements programs that develop learners' healthy habits of taking care of their health and exercising regularly.	1 (0.5%)	9 (4.5%)	40 (19.9%)	86 (42.8%)	65 (32.3%)	4.02	Highly Implemented
2. The school promotes learners' weight, height, and physical capacity up to set criteria.	3 (1.5%)	12 (6.0%)	50 (24.9%)	81 (40.3%)	55 (27.4%)	3.86	Moderately Implemented
3. The school implements policies that protect learners from harmful addictive substances and avoid conditions of risk related to violence, disease, accidents, and sexual problems.	2 (1.0%)	5 (2.5%)	33 (16.4%)	75 (37.3%)	86 (42.8%)	4.18	Highly Implemented
4. The school implements programs on developing confidence to self-express in an appropriate way and respect for others.	0 (0%)	9 (4.5%)	27 (13.4%)	65 (32.3%)	100 (49.8%)	4.27	Highly Implemented
5. The school develops in their learners the ability to have good human relationships with friends, teachers, and others.	1 (0.5%)	4 (2.0%)	32 (15.9%)	75 (37.3%)	89 (44.3%)	4.23	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.11	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Table 8 shows Standard 7, the level of implementation with which learners should have healthy habits and good physical and mental health. It shows that in indicator 4, the school implements programs on developing confidence to self-express in an appropriate way and respect for others, which obtained a weighted mean of 4.27. They firmly believe that private school teachers in Bangkok have different programs, projects, and activities that will develop the whole being of their learners.

In addition, there are also private school teachers in Bangkok that perceive that their schools should develop in their learners the ability to have good human relationships with friends, teachers, and others within and outside of the school premises, as stated in indicator 5, which garnered a 4.23 weighted mean.

Meanwhile, according to indicators 3 and 1, the private school teachers in Bangkok implement policies that protect learners from harmful addictive substances, avoid conditions of risk related to violence, disease, accidents, and sexual problems, and implement programs that develop learners' healthy habits of taking care of their health as well as exercising regularly, which obtained a 4.18 and 4.02 weighted mean, respectively.

Looking at indicator 2, the school promotes learners' weight, height, and physical capacity up to set criteria, which obtain a weighted mean of 3.86 and are described as moderately implemented. It seemed to reflect that some private school teachers in Bangkok have less focus on this specified health program.

Nevertheless, looking at the overall weighted mean of 4.11, the private school teachers in Bangkok are very highly implemented on all five indicators of Standard 7. They have a high regard for the learners' healthy habits in both physical and mental aspects.

Table 9. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Learners' Quality in terms of Standard 8*

S8. Learners should have a sense of aesthetics and a disposition for art, music, and sport.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The learners develop their ability to appreciating art, participate in artistic activities, and create artistic works.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	31 (15.4%)	56 (27.9%)	110 (54.7%)	4.35	Highly Implemented
2. The learners develop their appreciation for music or drama, participate in musical or dramatic activities, and create musical or dramatic works.	0 (0%)	8 (4.0%)	27 (13.4%)	61 (30.3%)	105 (52.2%)	4.31	Highly Implemented
3. The learners develop their appreciation for sport and recreation, participate in sport and recreational activities, and create sport and recreational works.	0 (0%)	7 (3.5%)	31 (15.4%)	54 (26.9%)	109 (54.2%)	4.32	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.33	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Table 9 presents the level of implementation of private schools in Bangkok on whether learners should have a sense of aesthetics and a disposition for art, music, and sport. As shown in the table, in indicator 1, the learners are developed in appreciating art, participating in activities, and creating artistic works, which garnered the highest weighted mean of 4.35 among the three indicators in this standard 8. It can be deduced the majority of private school teachers in Bangkok have implemented and integrated this indicator into their curriculum.

According to the weighted mean of 4.32 in indicator 3, private school teachers in Bangkok believed that their students should improve in appreciating sports and recreational activities and producing sports and recreational works. The weighted mean of 4.31 indicates that private school teachers in Bangkok also highly implemented programs for learners' development in music or drama, including participating in and creating musical or dramatic works, based on their standards.

The overall weighted mean of 4.33 indicates that private school teachers in Bangkok believed they implemented and complied with quality assurance standards highly and that their students had an aesthetic sense and a disposition for art, music, and sport.

On the next page with Table 10 provides an overview of the implementation levels of quality assurance mechanisms in Bangkok's private schools, revealing that the standards for student quality are being highly implemented across the board. With an average mean score of 4.23, it is clear that the students in these institutions meet a wide range of criteria related to both personal and academic development. These standards encompass essential qualities such as having strong virtues and morals, a profound understanding of environmental preservation, a strong work ethic, and the ability to work collaboratively. Furthermore, students demonstrate strong analytical skills, a love for continuous learning, good physical and mental health, and an appreciation for arts and sports. The standard receiving the highest implementation score (4.37) focuses on virtues, morality, and desirable values, highlighting the importance placed on character development. In contrast, the standard with the lowest score (4.07) still falls under the category of being highly implemented and pertains to students' knowledge and skills as outlined in the curriculum. This data collectively illustrates the effectiveness of quality assurance mechanisms in supporting well-rounded student growth in these private schools.

Table 10. *Summary of Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms in Terms of Standards of Learners' Quality*

Standards of Learners' Quality		
Standards	MEAN	DE
Standard 1: Learners should have virtues, morality, and desirable values.	4.37	Highly Implemented
Standard 2: Learners should be conscious of environmental preservation and development.	4.25	Highly Implemented
Standard 3: Learners should have a working skill, love to work, be able to work with others, and have a good attitude toward honest occupations.	4.30	Highly Implemented
Standard 4: Learners should have the abilities to think analytically and synthetically, have a good sense of judgment; be creative and thoughtful; and have a vision.	4.16	Highly Implemented
Standard 5: Learners should have the necessary knowledge and skills as prescribed by curricula.	4.07	Highly Implemented
Standard 6: Learners should have a skill for self-learning and love to learn and self-develop continuously.	4.23	Highly Implemented
Standard 7: Learners should have healthy habits and good physical and mental health.	4.11	Highly Implemented

Standard 8: Learners should have a sense of aesthetics and a disposition for art, music, and sport.	4.33	Highly Implemented
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.23	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Table 11. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Instruction in terms of Standard 9*

S9. Teachers should have virtues, morality, degrees, knowledge, and competence relevant to their responsibilities; maintain steady self-development; and be able to get along with communities. A sufficient number of teachers should be available.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The teachers possessed virtue and morality, behaving in accordance with a professional code of ethics.	1 (0.5%)	4 (2.0%)	23 (11.4%)	54 (26.9%)	119 (59.2%)	4.42	Highly Implemented
2. The teachers have good relationships with learners, guardians, and communities.	1 (0.5%)	3 (1.5%)	30 (14.9%)	43 (21.4%)	124 (61.7%)	4.42	Highly Implemented
3. The teachers have determination and devotion to teaching and developing learners.	2 (1.0%)	1 (0.5%)	21 (10.4%)	60 (29.9%)	117 (58.2%)	4.44	Highly Implemented
4. The teachers have a quest for new knowledge and techniques; they listen to opinions, are open-minded, and accept changes.	2 (1.0%)	6 (3.0%)	23 (11.4%)	64 (31.8%)	106 (52.7%)	4.32	Highly Implemented
5. The teachers have bachelor's degrees in education or equivalent.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	24 (11.9%)	59 (29.4%)	114 (56.7%)	4.41	Highly Implemented
6. The teachers teach subjects relevant to their major, minor, or aptitude.	1 (0.5%)	3 (1.5%)	32 (15.9%)	128 (63.7%)	37 (18.4%)	3.98	Moderately Implemented
7. There is a sufficient number of teachers and supporting staff.	3 (1.5%)	3 (1.5%)	42 (20.9%)	60 (29.9%)	93 (46.3%)	4.18	Highly Implemented

AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	4.31	Highly Implemented
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Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Table 11 presents the level of implementation of private schools in Bangkok in terms of teachers' virtues, morality, degrees, knowledge, and competence relevant to their responsibilities; maintaining steady self-development; and being able to get along with communities as indicated in Standard 9.

It can be gleaned from among the indicators that indicator 3, private school teachers in Bangkok, strongly believed and highly imposed that the teachers should have determination and devotion to teaching and developing learners, which obtained a weighted mean of 4.44.

On the other hand, indicators 1 and 2 affirm that private school teachers are convinced that teachers should possess virtue and morality, behave in accordance with a professional code of ethics, and have relationships with learners, guardians, and communities, which both obtained a weighted mean of 4.42. It is notable that private schools are highly implemented to employ teachers not only based on the degrees achieved but most importantly on their behavior, attitude, and character traits.

Moreover, private schools recruited teachers as declared in indicator 5 of the same table; the teachers should have bachelor's degrees in education or equivalent, which accumulated a weighted mean of 4.41, which means they are highly looking at the highest educational attainment to qualify for the teaching position.

Furthermore, the extent of compliance should be sufficient number of teachers and supporting staff is highly observable, as revealed by the weighted mean of 4.18 in indicator 7. While the teachers should teach subjects relevant to their major, minor, or aptitude, a 3.98 weighted mean was obtained. It manifests that some private schools moderately implemented this standard.

The overall weighted mean of 4.31 indicates a high level of implementation of Standard 9 in private schools in Bangkok. Private schools in Bangkok appear to maintain high standards in the selection and recruitment of their teachers and other staff.

Table 12, on the next page, presents the perceptions of private school teachers in Bangkok on the level of implementation with the standards on teachers having the ability to manage effective teaching and learning processes focusing on learner-centered instruction.

Indicator 2 reveals a deep-seated belief among private school teachers that they analyze learners' potential and understand them individually, resulting in a weighted mean of 4.44. This indicates that they closely monitor the development of each learner's abilities and capabilities. They also highly encourage teachers to refine the learners' outstanding potential.

It can be deemed on indicators 1, 4, and 5 that private school teachers perceive that teachers have knowledge of the goals of education, provisions, and the basic education curriculum; teachers are able to use technology to develop their own and learners' learning, and teachers evaluate teaching-learning outcomes congruent with the learning conditions arranged for learners and relative to learners' development as disclosed by the weighted mean of 4.43. It can be inferred that private school teachers have close monitoring of the learners' academic achievements and performance.

Table 12. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Instruction in terms of Standard 10*

S10. Teachers should have the ability to manage effective teaching and learning, especially learner-centered instruction.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The teachers have knowledge and understanding of the goals of education provision and the basic education curriculum.	1 (0.5%)	5 (2.5%)	20 (10.0%)	56 (27.9%)	119 (59.2%)	4.43	Highly Implemented
2. The teachers analyze the learners' potential and understand them individually.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	25 (12.4%)	50 (24.9%)	122 (60.7%)	4.44	Highly Implemented
3. The teachers are able to manage learner-centered instruction.	1 (0.5%)	4 (2.0%)	27 (13.4%)	53 (25.4%)	116 (57.7%)	4.39	Highly Implemented
4. The teachers are able to use technology to develop their own and the learners' learning.	0 (0%)	2 (1.0%)	24 (11.9%)	60. (29.9%)	115 (57.2%)	4.43	Highly Implemented
5. The teachers evaluate teaching-learning outcomes congruent with learning conditions arranged for learners and relative to learners' development.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	23 (11.4%)	57 (28.4%)	117 (58.2%)	4.43	Highly Implemented
6. The teachers use evaluation results to adjust instruction to develop learners to the best of their potential.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	23 (11.4%)	58 (28.9%)	116 (57.7%)	4.42	Highly Implemented
7. The teachers conduct research to improve learners' learning and use the results to improve learners.	2 (1.0%)	6 (3.0%)	27 (13.4%)	55 (27.4%)	111 (55.2%)	4.33	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.41	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Furthermore, private schools assumed that they hired teachers to evaluate the results of learners' performance to adjust instruction to develop learners to the best of their potential, as stipulated in indicator 6, which garnered a weighted mean of 4.42.

Additionally, indicators 3 and 7 indicate that teachers are able to manage learner-centered instruction and that teachers should conduct research to improve learners' performance both academically and through extracurricular activities that will enhance their inner potential, garnering a weighted mean of 4.39 and 4.33, respectively.

To summarize, the result of this table as Standard 10 conveys that private school teachers in Bangkok strongly believe that they are highly compliant with the programs, standards, and mandates of the Ministry of Education as well as their governing policies, goals, mission, and vision.

Table 13. *Summary of Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms in Terms of Standards of Instruction*

Standards of Instruction		
Standards	MEAN	DE
Standard 9: Teachers should have virtues, morality, degrees, knowledge, and competence relevant to their responsibilities; maintain steady self-development and be able to get along with communities. A sufficient number of teachers should be available.	4.31	Highly Implemented
Standard 10: Teachers should have the ability to manage effective teaching and learning, especially learner-centered instruction.	4.41	Highly Implemented
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.36	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

The data presented in Table 13 illustrates the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms in private schools in Bangkok, specifically in relation to the standards of instruction. The results show the degree to which school administrators uphold essential virtues, morality, leadership, and competence within the framework of managing educational institutions. For example, Standard 9, which emphasizes that teachers should possess virtues, morality, relevant degrees, knowledge, and competence while continuously improving themselves and maintaining good community relations, received a weighted mean of 4.31. The result indicates a high level of implementation, reflecting that private schools in Bangkok largely meet this standard. Similarly, Standard 10, which focuses on the ability of teachers to manage effective teaching and learning, particularly in a learner-centered approach, achieved a slightly higher weighted mean of 4.41, further suggesting strong adherence to this quality assurance criterion.

In conclusion, the overall weighted mean for the standards of instruction is 4.36, categorizing it as "Highly Implemented" according to the scale provided, where scores ranging from 3.51 to 4.50 indicate high implementation. This means that private schools in Bangkok are not only meeting but excelling in ensuring their teachers and administrators align with the expected quality standards. The data reinforces that these schools are highly compliant in fostering an environment of continuous professional development, ethical conduct, and effective teaching practices.

Table 14. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Educational Administration and Management in terms of Standard 11*

S11. Administrators should have virtues, morality, leadership, and competence in educational administration and management.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school administrators practiced good virtues and morality and behaved in accordance with a professional code of ethics.	1 (0.5%)	3 (1.5%)	26 (12.9%)	63 (31.3%)	108 (53.7%)	4.36	Highly Implemented
2. The administrators show creativity, vision, and academic leadership.	2 (1.0%)	7 (3.5%)	39 (19.4%)	75 (37.3%)	78 (38.8%)	4.09	Highly Implemented
3. The administrators show ability in academic administration and management.	2 (1.0%)	8 (4.0%)	39 (19.4%)	73 (36.3%)	79 (39.3%)	4.09	Highly Implemented
4. The administrators have an effective and efficient administration that satisfies the involved people.	3 (1.5%)	7 (3.5%)	49 (24.4%)	68 (33.8%)	74 (36.8%)	4.01	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.14	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Table 14 presents the level of implementation of private schools in Bangkok in terms of administrators' virtues, morality, leadership and competence in educational administration and management as indicated in Standard 11.

On the same table, indicators 2 and 3 show that administrators are creative, visionary, and competent at leading, managing and administering academically, as evident by the weighted mean of 4.09.

Moreover, private school teachers perceived that their administrators are effective and efficient in administering their school personnel, garnering a 4.01 weighted mean. We can infer that they are qualified administrators not only to the school personnel but also the school stakeholders and community.

To sum up, it can be concluded that private school respondents in Bangkok comply with Standard 11 of quality assurance, as school administrators possess the necessary virtues, morality, leadership, and competence in educational administration and management. The weighted means for all indicators are above 4, showing that administrators exhibit good behavior, demonstrate academic leadership, possess

academic administration and management skills, and maintain an effective and efficient administration that satisfies stakeholders. The overall mean of 4.14 indicates a high level of implementation of this standard.

On the next page, Table 15 transpires the level of implementation with quality assurance mechanisms of private schools in Bangkok as Standard 12 that educational institutions should establish an organizational and instructional structure, foster organizational development and maintain a comprehensive organization system. Private schools have well-thought-out organization, structural, and administrative systems that can be easily changed to fit different situations. This is clear from the fact that indicator 1 has the highest weighted mean (4.15), out of the five indicators.

Table 15. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Educational Administration and Management in terms of Standard 12*

S12. Educational institutions should have an organizational and structural arrangement, administrative systems, and organizational development that are holistic and systematic.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school arranges organization, structure, and administrative systems that are highly flexible and adjustable in response to situations.	1 (0.5%)	8 (4.0%)	34 (16.9%)	74 (36.8%)	84 (41.8%)	4.15	Highly Implemented
2. The school manages information such that it becomes systematic, comprehensive, and readily accessible.	3 (1.5%)	6 (3.0%)	42 (20.9%)	77 (38.3%)	73 (36.3%)	4.05	Highly Implemented
3. The school implements a continuous internal system of quality assurance.	3 (1.5%)	7 (3.5%)	45 (22.4%)	83 (41.3%)	63 (31.3%)	3.98	Moderately Implemented
4. The school manages the systematic and continuous development of personnel.	2 (1.0%)	7 (3.5%)	47 (23.4%)	85 (42.3%)	60 (29.9%)	3.97	Moderately Implemented
5. The school implements a system for measuring client satisfaction with service and involves people in administration and learner development.	2 (1.0%)	6 (3.0%)	47 (23.4%)	77 (38.3%)	69 (34.3%)	4.02	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.03	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Teachers also agree that private schools in Bangkok are well-known, that they follow Standard 12, that they keep information organized so that it is systemic, complete, and easy to find when needed, that they set up a way to find out how happy customers are with their service, and that they involve people in administration and learner development (with a weighted mean of 4.05 and 4.02, respectively). This means that private educational institutions in Bangkok highly practice the delegating leadership style.

Based on the same table, indicators 3 and 4 are moderately used by the private schools. This is because they have an ongoing internal system for quality assurance and manage staff development in a planned and ongoing way, as shown by the weighted mean scores of 3.98 and 3.97, respectively. It can be noted that private educational institutions in Bangkok had less weight on the implementation of the continuity of the internal system of quality assurance and staff professional growth and development.

As shown in Table 15, it can be inferred that private school teachers in Bangkok generally comply with the quality assurance standard on organizational and structural arrangements, administrative systems, and organizational development. The indicators have a relatively high weighted mean, with the overall mean being 4.03, indicating that these schools prioritize and implement measures to ensure a holistic and systematic educational institution. However, there may still be some areas for improvement, particularly in the continuous internal system of quality assurance and personnel development, which have slightly lower mean scores. Nonetheless, it is still apparent that private school respondents in Bangkok are committed to complying with quality assurance standards to provide quality education for their students.

Table 16. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Educational Administration and Management in terms of Standard 13*

S13. Educational institutions should have educational administration and management with school-based indicators.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school decentralizes educational administration and management.	3 (1.5%)	10 (5.0%)	39 (19.4%)	82 (40.8%)	67 (33.3%)	4	Highly Implemented
2. The school uses strategic administration and principles of participation.	2 (1.0%)	6 (3.0%)	41 (20.4%)	79 (39.3%)	73 (36.3%)	4.07	Highly Implemented
3. The school has a school committee that takes part in school development.	4 (2.0%)	6 (3.0%)	38 (18.9%)	84 (41.8%)	69 (34.3%)	4.03	Highly Implemented
4. The school uses a performance-based administrative style.	3 (1.5%)	8 (4.0%)	35 (17.4%)	91 (45.3%)	64 (31.8%)	4.02	Highly Implemented
5. The school undertakes a check and balance system.	2 (1.0%)	8 (4.0%)	58 (28.9%)	93 (46.3%)	40 (19.9%)	3.8	Moderately Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						3.98	Moderately Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Table 16 presents the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms of private schools in Bangkok with Standard 13 on whether educational institutions should have educational administration and management with school-based indicators. Indicator 2 shows that schools use strategic administration and principles of participation, obtaining a weighted mean of 4.07 which is described as highly implemented. This means private school teachers in Bangkok perceive that their administrators in Bangkok practice a collaboration, participatory, and consultative style of leadership.

It can be added that private schools in Bangkok have different school committees that take part in school development as evidenced by a weighted mean of 4.03 in indicator 3, which means that the delegation style of management is highly implemented.

Furthermore, private school teachers in Bangkok strongly believe that they use a performance-based administrative and management style that is very evident by the weighted mean of 4.02. It can be perceived that educational institutions place a high value on performance management styles. They are particular about giving of feedback to school teachers, personnel and other employees to institute growth goals and provide support systems for their employees' professional growth and development.

It can be noticed that indicator 5 of the same table received less attention in their administration and management of the check and balance system as reflected by the weighted mean of 3.80, which is moderately implemented.

On top of that, the overall weighted mean of 3.98 indicates that compliance with this standard is moderately implemented, which can lead to the improvement of quality education and better outcomes for students. Private school teachers in Bangkok recognize the importance of having effective educational administration and management practices for the overall success of their institution. This compliance highlights the commitment of these schools to providing quality education to their students and the community they serve.

Table 17 . *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Education Administration and Management in Term of Standard 14*

S14. Educational institutions should have learner-centered curricula and learning processes.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school has a curriculum suitable for learners and communities.	1 (0.5%)	3 (1.5%)	18 (9.0%)	65 (32.3%)	114 (56.7%)	4.43	Highly Implemented
2. The school arranges diverse subjects and activities for learners to choose according to their interests.	3 (1.5%)	2 (1.0%)	24 (11.9%)	79 (39.3%)	93 (46.3%)	4.28	Highly Implemented
3. The school encourages teachers to design instructional plans sensitive to learners' aptitudes and abilities.	3 (1.5%)	4 (2.0%)	27 (13.4%)	62 (30.8%)	105 (52.2%)	4.3	Highly Implemented

4. The school promotes and develops instructional innovations, instructional media, and instruments that support learning.	3 (1.5%)	4 (2.0%)	25 (12.4%)	74 (36.8%)	95 (47.3%)	4.26	Highly Implemented
5. The school has systematized the recording, reporting, and transfer of learners' data.	0 (0%)	4 (2.0%)	28 (13.9%)	69 (34.3%)	100 (49.8%)	4.32	Highly Implemented
6. The school has a system of instructional supervision and uses supervisors' comments to regularly improve instruction.	2 (1.0%)	4 (2.0%)	29 (14.4%)	74 (36.8%)	92 (45.8%)	4.24	Highly Implemented
7. The school incorporates local learning resources and wisdom into its instruction.	3 (1.5%)	9 (4.5%)	29 (14.4%)	68 (33.8%)	92 (45.8%)	4.18	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.29	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Based on the Table 17, the data present the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms standards in private schools in Bangkok that educational institutions should have learner-centered curricula and learning processes as Standard 14. Indicator 1 demonstrates that the schools have created curricula that are tailored to the needs and interests of their students, achieving the highest weighted mean of 4.43. This indicates that they are effectively implementing the standard.

It can be noticed in indicator 5 that the schools have systematized recording, reporting and transferring of learners' data, garnering a weighted mean of 4.32, which is also highly implemented in most private schools in Bangkok. While indicator 3 shows how schools' teachers are encouraged to create instructional plans that consider the learners' abilities, as evidently proven by weighted mean of 4.30, which is also highly implemented in all schools in Bangkok.

Scrutinizing indicators 2, 4 and 6 it can be perceived that private school respondents in Bangkok generally comply with the standard on arranged diversity in subjects and activities for learners to choose according to their interests; the schools also promote the use of innovative instructional media and instruments that support learning, and teachers are encouraged to create instructional plans that consider the learners' abilities, which are evidently supported by their weighted mean of 4.28, 4.26 and 4.24, respectively. Private school teachers in Bangkok believed that they highly implemented these three indicators as transpired in Standard 14.

With an overall weighted mean of 4.29, which is highly implemented, it is inferred that the private schools in Bangkok have been successful and continuous in complying with this standard and providing a learner-centered education for their students.

Table 18. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Education Administration and Management 15*

S15. Educational institutions should have diverse activities to promote learners' qualities.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school has developed a strong and all-inclusive system of learner assistance.	3 (1.5%)	5 (2.5%)	33 (16.4%)	55 (27.4%)	105 (52.2%)	4.26	Highly Implemented
2. The school arranges activities that promote and respond to learners' academic and creative abilities.	1 (0.5%)	8 (4.0%)	32 (15.9%)	52 (25.9%)	108 (53.7%)	4.28	Highly Implemented
3. The school arranges activities that promote and respond to learners' special abilities and aptitudes to their full potential.	3 (1.5%)	7 (3.5%)	38 (18.9%)	56 (27.9%)	97 (48.3%)	4.18	Highly Implemented
4. The school arranges activities that promote good social values.	2 (1.0%)	4 (2.0%)	28 (13.9%)	58 (28.9%)	109 (54.2%)	4.33	Highly Implemented
5. The school arranges activities that promote art, music, traditional dance, and sport or recreation.	1 (0.5%)	5 (2.5%)	26 (12.9%)	57 (28.4%)	112 (55.7%)	4.36	Highly Implemented
6. The school arranges activities that continue and create culture, custom, tradition, and Thai wisdom.	1 (0.5%)	2 (1.0%)	28 (13.9%)	73 (36.3%)	97 (48.3%)	4.31	Highly Implemented
7. The school arranges activities that promote the spirit of democracy.	1 (0.5%)	8 (4.0%)	42 (20.9%)	77 (38.3%)	73 (36.3%)	4.06	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.25	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Table 18 shows the level of implementation of quality assurance standards in private schools in Bangkok; educational institutions should have diverse activities to promote learners' qualities stipulated in Standard 15. Indicator 5 shows that private school teachers in Bangkok believed that there is a high level of implementation of recreational activities promoting art, music, traditional dance, and sports to develop students' artistic talents, as shown in their weighted mean of 4.36.

However, respondents' private schools in Bangkok stated that they provide activities for students to learn and practice values that foster positive relationships, obtaining a weighted mean of 4.33, which is highly implemented, as indicated in indicator 4. They also provide activities that will continue to make them proud of their culture, customs, traditions, and Thai wisdom, as reflected by the weighted mean of

4.31 in indicator 6. It can be gleaned that they strongly implemented activities that continue to preserve and promote Thai cultural heritage while instilling a sense of pride and appreciation in the students.

It also appears that private school teachers in Bangkok believe that they focus on promoting activities that nurture the unique talents and strengths of each student. Ultimately, these activities enable students to maximize their abilities and reach their highest potential, as evidenced by the weighted mean of 4.28 in indicator 2.

Furthermore, teacher who answered thought that private schools in Bangkok had a good system in place to help all students, making sure that all of them got the help they needed to do well in school, in their personal lives, and with their friends. Indicator 1's 4.26 weighted mean confirms this.

The data in indicators 3 and 7 can be sufficient to show that private school teachers in Bangkok fully promoted activities that respondents to the learners' special aptitude to their full potential, as exhibited by weighted mean of 4.18 and 4.06, respectively, which means they highly implemented and campaigned to support in their school community that the sense of belongingness is felt by every learner.

To generalize, it is very evident that private schools in Bangkok are highly compliant with Standard 15 as reflected by the overall weighted mean of 4.25. They all have diverse activities that cater to and enhance the learners' abilities, capabilities, and qualities.

Table 19, presented on the next page, shows that educational institutions play a huge role in shaping the development of learners, and incorporating environmental arrangements and services that promote their natural development is essential. First, indicators 2 of Standard 16 demonstrates how private schools in Bangkok highly promoted learners' health and safety as reflected by the weighted mean of 4.28. This means that they believe that in their schools their learners and teachers are safe and free from any suspicious incidents.

Second, indicator 1 shows that respondents from private school in Bangkok strongly believed that they were in favor of providing suitable infrastructure to make a good learning environment that puts safety and accessibility of the building facilities with safety regulations first, with a weighted mean score of 4.25.

Third, the weighted mean of 4.24 shows that private school teachers in Bangkok think that they offer a range of IT services to support students' self-learning and participatory learning. These services include giving students with access to educational resources and letting work together to learn using technology that prepares students for the digital skills they will need in today's connected world, as shown in indicator 3.

Table 19. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Education Community Development 16*

S16. Educational institutions should have environmental arrangements and services that promote learners' natural development to the best of their potential.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school provides a learning-supportive environment and suitable buildings and places.	1 (0.5%)	6 (3.0%)	35 (17.4%)	58 (28.9%)	101 (50.2%)	4.25	Highly Implemented
2. The school promotes learners' health and safety.	0 (0%)	8 (4.0%)	28 (13.9%)	64 (31.8%)	101 (50.2%)	4.28	Highly Implemented

3. The school provides all sorts of information technology services that support self-learning and participatory learning.	0 (0%)	8 (4.0%)	28 (13.9%)	72 (35.8%)	93 (46.3%)	4.24	Highly Implemented
4. The school provides sufficient and functional classrooms, labs, libraries, green areas, and facilities.	1 (0.5%)	4 (2.0%)	34 (16.9%)	73 (36.3%)	89 (44.3%)	4.22	Highly Implemented
5. The school provides and uses learning resources both inside and outside school.	1 (0.5%)	2 (1.0%)	40 (19.9%)	80 (39.8%)	78 (38.8%)	4.15	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.23	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

For the fourth indicator, the weighted mean score of 4.22 shows that private schools in Bangkok are using IT services to make learning more interactive, giving students access to a lot of new information, ideas, and experiences. In addition, this indicator denotes a highly implemented strategy that utilizes various resources to expand students' knowledge bases, encourages independent learning, and caters to different learning styles, which broadens learning opportunities by accessing learning resources outside the classroom. Students can leverage libraries, museums, community centers, and green areas; this fosters a lifelong love for learning.

Finally, indicator 5, with a weighted mean of 4.15, denotes that the private school teachers in Bangkok believed that they provide and utilize learning resources both inside and outside of the school to deepen students' understanding and foster a lifelong love for learning and self-motivated education.

The overall weighted mean of 4.23, which indicates a high implementation rate, demonstrates how private schools in Bangkok are fostering important 21st-century skills and learners' natural development to boost students' success.

The data, which are displayed in Table 20 on the next page, suggest that private schools in Bangkok are highly implemented and in compliance with Standard 17 of quality assurance.

With a weighted mean of 4.16, the first indicator measures how well the school is connected to the community's knowledge and learning resources. This analysis shows that private school teachers in Bangkok perceive that they are actively utilizing local knowledge and resources, such as community leaders and cultural institutions, to improve their educational offerings. Such activity is a crucial component of quality control because it guarantees that educational institutions are educating students in a way that is both culturally and contextually relevant.

Table 20. *Summary of Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms in Terms of Standards of Educational Administration and Management*

Standards of Educational Administration and Management		
Standards	MEAN	DE
Standard 11: Administrators should have virtues, morality, leadership, and	4.14	Highly Implemented

competence in educational administration and management.		
Standard 12: Educational institutions should have an organizational and structural arrangement, administrative systems, and organizational development that are holistic and systematic.	4.03	Highly Implemented
Standard 13: Educational institutions should have educational administration and management with school-based indicators.	3.98	Highly Implemented
Standard 14: Educational institutions should have learner-centered curricula and learning processes.	4.29	Highly Implemented
Standard 15: Educational institutions should have diverse activities to promote learners' qualities.	4.25	Highly Implemented
Standard 16: Educational institutions should have environmental arrangements and services that promote learners natural development to the best of their potential.	4.23	Highly Implemented
OVERALL MEAN	4.17	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Table 21. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Learning and Community Development Standard 17*

S17. Educational institutions should provide support and use local learning resources and wisdom.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school links with and exchanges information with local learning resources and wisdom.	1 (0.5%)	9 (4.5%)	32 (15.9%)	74 (36.8%)	85 (42.3%)	4.16	Highly Implemented
2. The school provides support for the use of learning resources, wisdom, and community to participate in the design of school-based curriculum.	2 (1.0%)	7 (3.5%)	39 (19.4%)	74 (36.8%)	79 (39.3%)	4.1	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.13	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

Examining the weighted mean of 4.10 for the second indicator shows how well the school supports the use of learning resources and involves the community in curriculum planning. The evidence shows that private school teachers in Bangkok believe they are actively involving their communities in developing their curricula, which is another crucial component of quality assurance. It seemed that schools could ensure that their programs are pertinent to the needs and interests of their students and the larger community by incorporating the community in the curriculum design process.

Generally, private school teachers in Bangkok believe that they adhere very closely to Standard 17 of quality assurance, according to the overall weighted mean of 4.13. This indicates that these institutions are strongly all-out dedicated to offering top-notch education that is both current and sensitive to cultural differences.

Table 22. *Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on Standards of Learning and Community Development Standard 18*

S18. Educational institutions should cooperate with families, religious organizations, academic institutions, and public and private organizations to develop learning paths in communities.	1	2	3	4	5	WM	DE
1. The school serves as an academic resource in a quest for knowledge and community service.	2 (1.0%)	6 (3.0%)	28 (13.9%)	73 (36.3%)	92 (45.8%)	4.23	Highly Implemented
2. The school implements programs for exchanging knowledge in a mutual manner with the community groups.	1 (0.5%)	6 (3.0%)	36 (17.9%)	83 (41.3%)	75 (37.3%)	4.12	Highly Implemented
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN						4.18	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

As shown in Table 22, private school teachers in Bangkok perceived that they are playing important roles as academic resources and contributors to community service. In accordance with their weighted mean of 4.23, it can be said that the majority of schools at Bangkok's private schools support collaboration with families, academic institutions, and public and private groups to develop learning paths in communities.

To achieve the possible benefits according to their weighted mean of 4.12 implies that private schools in Bangkok implemented initiatives that encourage learning, personal and community engagement, and encourage students to support their communities through fundraising or volunteering.

The overall weighted mean of Standard 18 is 4.18, indicating that private school teachers in Bangkok play a vital role as an academic resource in the pursuit of knowledge and community services catering to diverse learning needs.

Table 23. *Summary of Level of Implementation of Quality Assurance Mechanisms in Terms of Standards of Learning and Community Development*

Standards of Learning and Community Development		
Standards	MEAN	DE
Standard 17: Educational institutions should provide support and use local learning resources and wisdom.	4.13	Highly Implemented
Standard 18: Educational institutions should cooperate with families, religious organizations, academic institutions, and public and private organizations to develop learning paths in communities.	4.18	Highly Implemented
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.15	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1 1.00-1.50 (Least Implemented) 2 1.51-2.50 (Slightly Implemented) 3 2.51 - 3.50 (Moderately Implemented) 4 3.51-4.50 (Highly Implemented) 5 4.51- 5 (Very Highly Implemented)

As shown in Table 23 based on the summary of level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms in terms of standards of learning and community development, an overall weighted mean of 4.15 exhibits as highly implemented. Community development of Standard 18 emphasizes on educational institutions should cooperate with families, religious organizations, academic institutions, and public and private organizations to develop learning paths in communities is highly implemented compared to Standard 17 Educational institutions should provide support and use local learning resources.

Table 24. *Correlation between the Implementation Level of Standards of Learners' Quality and Profile Variables*

Variables	Chi-Square	p-value	Conclusion
Number of enrollees	223.335	0.002	Significant
Number of teaching staff	135.263	0.405	Not Significant
Number of non-teaching staff	146.209	0.188	Not Significant
Faculty and student ratio	144.536	0.215	Not Significant
Type of curriculum used	214.578	0.199	Not Significant
Number of awards received	163.149	0.034	Significant
Number of Extracurricular Activities	211.855	0	Significant

The correlation between the implementation of standards of learners' quality and profile variables The extent of implementation of standards of learners' quality in terms of the number of enrollees, the number of awards received, and the number of extracurricular activities has significant relationships. However, it indicates that there is no significant link between the respondents' level of implementation and profile variables like the number of teaching staff, non-teaching staff, faculty-to-student ratio, and curriculum type.

Table 25. *Correlation between the Implementation Level of Standards of Instruction and Profile Variables*

Variables	Chi-Square	p-value	Conclusion
Number of enrollees	223.335	0.002	Significant
Number of teaching staff	135.263	0.405	Not Significant
Number of non-teaching staff	146.209	0.188	Not Significant
Faculty and student ratio	144.536	0.215	Not Significant
Type of curriculum used	214.578	0.199	Not Significant
Number of awards received	163.149	0.034	Significant
Number of Extracurricular Activities	211.855	0.000	Significant

The correlation between the implementation level of standards of instruction and profile variables, such as the number of enrollees, number of awards received, and the number of extracurricular activities, has significant relationships. On the other hand, it indicates that the number of teaching staff, the number of non-teaching staff, the faculty-student ratio, and the type of curriculum used to have no significant relationships.

Table 26. *Correlation between the Implementation Level of Standards of Educational Administration & Management and the Profile Variables*

Variables	Chi-Square	p-value	Conclusion
Number of enrollees	782.565	0.165	Not Significant
Number of teaching staff	652.841	0.053	Not Significant
Number of non-teaching staff	645.693	0.078	Not Significant
Faculty and student ratio	654.984	0.47	Significant
Type of curriculum used	905.347	0.389	Not Significant
Number of awards received	634.19	0.135	Not Significant
Number of Extracurricular Activities	663.627	0.028	Significant

The correlation between the implementation level of standards of educational administration and management and profile variables like faculty and student ratio and the number of extracurricular activities has significant relationships. However, there are no significant relationships between the number of enrollees, the number of teaching staff, the number of non-teaching staff, the type of curriculum used, and the number of awards received.

Table 27. *Correlation between the Implementation Level of Standards of Learning & Community Development and the Profile Variables*

Variables	Chi-Square	p-value	Conclusion
Number of enrollees	89.88	0.022	Significant
Number of teaching staff	78.82	0.010	Significant
Number of non-teaching staff	60.625	0.193	Not Significant
Faculty and student ratio	56.424	0.313	Not Significant

Type of curriculum used	107.207	0.016	Significant
Number of awards received	90.088	0.001	Significant
Number of Extracurricular Activities	98.859	0.000	Significant

The number relation between the implementation level of standards of learning and community development and profile variables such as the number of enrollees, the number of teaching staff, the type of curriculum used, the number of awards received, and the number of extracurricular activities has significant relationships. Likewise, it demonstrated that the ratio of non-teaching staff to faculty and students has no significant relationship.

Proposed Sustainability Plan in the Implementation of the Quality Assurance Mechanisms of Private Schools in Bangkok, Thailand

Based on the findings, here is the suggested sustainability plan for the private schools in Bangkok

Standards	Objectives	Key Performance Indicator	Program Project Activities	Time Frame	Person Involved	Source of Fund	Expected Outcome
Learner's Quality	To increase the average of National Aptitude Test (SAT)	10- Excellent 8 to 9-Very Satisfactory 5-6-7- Satisfactory 3-4- Poor 0-2 Needs Improvement	Conduct after school class focusing on SAT Provision of materials for reviewing SATS takers	October 2023 April 2024	Administration Department Heads Teachers Resource SAT teachers	20,000 Thai Baht / Month \$110 (3816 THB) SAT Test	75-90% passed the test
	To promote learners' weight, height, and physical capacity up to set criteria.	Based on BMI	Conduct monthly monitoring of height and weight	September 2023 to June 2024	School Nurse Teacher	No budget needed	75-90% student normal BMI

Standards of Instruction	To provide teachers' subjects relevant to their major, minor, or aptitude.	Provision of Quality Curriculum Teacher Academic Skills Teacher experience Lesson Planning and Student Assessment System	Curriculum developing per department Teacher mentoring/Peer observation INSET in house or outsource experts Prepare daily lesson plan and activity log Regular monitoring of lesson plans and evaluation of student learning and achievement	August 2023 May 2024	Administration and school Heads Head of Departments Teachers and Staff	500,000 Thai Baht / year	100% of teachers observed 100% of teachers attended 100% utilized
	To manage the systematic and continuous development of personnel.	Depends of the number of teachers	Circle time using Personal, Social, Health Economic Education (PSHE) Staff support	August 2023 June 2024	Administration Teachers and other staff	5,000 per teacher for PD	60% of staff
Educational Administration and Management	To improve school manages the systematic and continuous development	Depends on the number of staff	Training needs assessment Continuous professional development training Quarterly and Annual management plan and implementation Development and operation of education management information system	August 2023 June 2023	Administration Head of Departments Coordinators Non-teaching staff	1,000,000 Thai Baht / year	Annual implementation plan

	To undertake check and balance systems	Subject areas coordinator	Curriculum alignment Monitoring by subject area	September 2023 June 2024	Administration Department head Coordinators Teacher	500,000 thb	100% complied
Learning and Community Development	To implement programs for exchanging knowledge in mutual manners with the community group	Improved community engagement Health and Hygiene Practices and Sporting Activities	Meetings and engagement with school management committees Community outreach Parent-teacher meetings Health and hygiene plan Demonstrated healthy practices of students Sports and games facilities, and events plan	August 2023 June 2024	Head of Departments Local community officials Abbot / Monks / Priest / Pastor Health officials Doctors / Nurses / Rescue	500,000 Thai Baht / year	100% participated
	Provide and support for the use of learning sources, and participate in designing school-based curriculum.	Based on the number of activities conducted	Community outreach program Invite community human resource expert	September 2023 June 2024	Administration School heads Teachers Parents	200,000 thb	100% participated

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS

Profile of the Respondents

The total number of respondents was 201. The majority of respondents had 301 to 500 students per school year, or 27.4%; 2001 and above had 44 frequencies, or 21.9 percent; 101 to 300 students per school year came in third with 35 frequencies, or 17.4%; 1001 to 2000 students per school year came in fourth with 34 frequencies, or 16.9%; and finally, 501 to 1000 students per school year came in fifth with 30 frequencies, or 14.9 percent.

According to the data, the frequency of teaching staff among respondents is 65, or 45.3%, with 35, or 17.4%, coming in second. Following those are 34, or 16.9%; 33, or 16.4%; and finally 8, or 4%.

It also reveals that the number of non-teaching staff among respondents has 65 highest frequencies, or 32.3%, followed by 47 frequencies, or 23.4%, then 35 frequencies, or 17.4%, and then 27 frequencies, or 13.4%, and lastly, we had 16 to 20 and 21 to 25 numbers of non-teaching staff with the same 27 frequencies, or 13.4%.

The highest frequency of the teacher-student ratio is 70 frequencies, or 34.8%. 45 frequencies, or 22.4%, come in second place after 53 frequencies, or 26.4%. Following it are 12 frequencies, or 6.0%, and 21 frequencies, or 10.4%, which are both ranked fourth.

It demonstrates that the majority of the curriculum used by the respondents is the Ministry of Education Curriculum Thailand (English Program) with 46 frequencies, or 22.9%, next in rank is Ministry of Education Thailand (Bilingual and Mini-Bilingual Programme) with 42 frequencies, or 20.9%, ranked three is National Curriculum of England with 36 frequencies, or 17.9%, followed by American Curriculum rank as fourth with 33 frequencies, or 16.4%, then fifth rank is British Columbia Curriculum (BC, Canada) with 21 frequencies, or 10.4%, furthermore, International Baccalaureate Curriculum (IB) with 7 frequencies, or 3.5%, Singapore Curriculum and Australian Curriculum shared the seventh rank with 3 frequencies, or 1.5%, then Canadian Curriculum with 2 frequencies, or 1.0%, and finally, Cambridge Curriculum, Canadian Curriculum/Thailand English Program, CBSE, Child and Life-Centered, Ontario Curriculum, Singapore/UK Curriculum, and Singapore/British Curriculum shared the ninth rank with 1 frequency, or 0.5%.

Number of awards received: out of 201 respondents, it shows that 0 to 10 awards received are 64 or 31%, then next in rank is 45 frequencies, or 22.4% awards received; however, 16 to 20 and 26 to 30 and above numbers of awards received rank third by 38 frequencies, or 18.9%, and lastly, 21 to 25 with 16 frequencies, or 8.0% awards received.

The highest frequency of extracurricular activities per year is 76, or 37.8%; the second is 72, or 35.8%; the third rank is 22 frequencies, or 10.9%; the fourth is 17 frequencies, or 8.5%; and the fifth is 14 frequencies, or 7.0%.

The extent to which private schools in Thailand implement quality assurance mechanisms

Learner quality standards: based on the responses of 201 teachers and department heads, the degree of implementation was calculated to be 4.23 or "higher."

Standard of instruction: the total number of respondents who provided data and findings resulted in an overall weighted mean of 4.36, which corresponds to "high" in implementation.

Standards of educational administration and management: The total number of respondents, collected data, and findings yielded an overall weighted mean of 4.17, interpreted as "high" in implementation.

Standards of learning and community development are very well implemented, with a mean score of 4.15 according to the data collected from respondents.

Overall, the extent of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms in Thai private schools in Bangkok was "highly implemented," with an overall mean value of 4.23.

Specifically, the quality assurance mechanism of Bangkok's private schools was "implemented" with a mean value of 4.23, and standards A, B, C, and D had respective mean values of 4.23, 4.36, 4.17, and 4.15.

Relationship between the level of implementation of the quality assurance mechanisms used by private schools and the school's profile variables?

The correlation between the implementation of standards of learners' quality and profile variables. The extent of implementation of standards of learners' quality in terms of the number of enrollees, the number of awards received, and the number of extracurricular activities have significant relationships. However, it displays that the level of implementation of the respondents and their profile variables, such as

the number of teaching staff, the number of non-teaching staff, the faculty-student ratio, and the type of curriculum used, have no significant relationship.

The correlation between the implementation level of standards of instruction and profile variables such as the number of enrollees, number of awards received, and number of extracurricular activities has significant relationships. On the other hand, it shows that the number of teaching staff, the number of non-teaching staff, the faculty-student ratio, and the type of curriculum used have no significant relationships.

The correlation between the implementation level of standards of educational administration and management and profile variables like faculty and student ratio and the number of extracurricular activities has significant relationships. Whereas the number of enrollees, the number of teaching staff, the number of non-teaching staff, the type of curriculum used, and the number of awards received show no significant relationships.

The number relation between the implementation level of standards of learning and community development and profile variables such as the number of enrollees, the number of teaching staff, the type of curriculum used, the number of awards received, and the number of extracurricular activities has significant relationships. Likewise, it demonstrated that the ratio of non-teaching staff to faculty and students has no significant relationship.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the study's findings, the following conclusions are reached:

1. Most of the respondents' student population ranges from 500 and below with a 26 or above number of teaching staff and non-teaching staff; the student and teacher ratio does not exceed 25 students per class; the majority of the curriculum used with our respondents is the Ministry of Education curriculum (bilingual and/or mini-bilingual); ten or fewer awards are received every year; and schools offer innumerable extracurricular activities.
2. The level of implementation of the quality assurance mechanisms in terms of standards of learners' quality, standards of instructions, standards of educational administration and management and standards of learning and community development is highly implemented.
3. There is no significant relationship between the extent of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms utilized by private schools and the school's profile variables in terms of the number of enrollees, the number of teaching staff, extracurricular activities, and the number of awards received.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusion, the following quality assurance procedures could be offered to enhance or improve the management of private schools in Bangkok:

1. Based on the findings and conclusion it showed that fewer awards are received every year. It is recommended however, to prepare a list of activities aiming to join inter school competition, national competition and international competition that will give awards and recognition to respective schools.
2. Based on the findings and conclusion the result showed that the level of implementation of the quality assurance mechanisms in terms of standards of learners' quality, standards of instructions, standards of educational administration and management and standards of learning and community development is highly implemented. Although it is highly implemented it is therefore recommended to all private school's administrators, principals, department heads, teachers to adapt and create sustainability plan.

3. Based on the findings and conclusion the result showed that there is no significant relationship between the extent of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms utilized by private schools and the school's profile variables in terms of the number of enrollees, the number of teaching staff, extracurricular activities, and the number of awards received. Therefore, it is highly recommended to public and private schools/institutions to conduct service training and professional development for school administrators, teachers, and school staff.
4. Finally, similar research should be conducted for wider scope involving quality assurance mechanisms in terms of standards of learners' quality, standards of instructions, standards of educational administration and management and standards of learning and community development and its implications to the performance of learners and schools.

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